

In the Name of God

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**A Critical Discourse Analysis of Conversations in the Iranian Textbook
Vision 3 Based on Fairclough's Model With Pedagogical Implications
for English Language Teaching**

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In the name of God, The Most Merciful, The Most Compassionate

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Dedicated to

*... my family, for their endless love and support throughout
all my life*

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Abstract

The aim of this thesis was to conduct a critical discourse analysis of conversations in Vision 3 textbook based on Fairclough's three-dimensional model. Analysis of the contents, topics, themes, characters, situations, contexts and textual characteristics of the conversations revealed that the ideological and cultural aspects and elements of the conversations include predominance of male characters, valuing knowledge and education, honoring national history, culture and famous figures, nationalism, patriotism and encouragement for curiosity. The analysis also showed that the conversations were inauthentic, unrealistic and unnatural. Implications and possible benefits of adapting and integrating critical discourse analysis in teaching English language include revision of the materials and instructional texts, development of supplementary and compensational materials and activities, and improvement of critical thinking among the learners.

Keywords: critical discourse analysis, Fairclough's three dimensional model, instructional conversations, textbooks, Vision 3

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Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 General Overview

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is defined as an area of academic inquiry and a research paradigm in sociolinguistics which considers discourse or language use as social practice within specific social contexts. It studies, surveys and analyzes the dialectic, internal and dynamic relationship between discourse and power, ideology, inequality and social relations. Critical discourse analysis is a field of sociolinguistic research which aims to identify and examine the relationship between language use and elements of social relations such as power and dominance, system of values and ideology, inequality and social change. Its main notion and fundamental concept is that language use is related to social relations by essence and the relationship between the way people use language and the social context in which they are involved, is dialectic and bilateral (Fairclough, 1989, 1992a, 1993, 1995a, 1998, 2001 & 2002; Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 1999).

Critical discourse analysis is an approach to linguistic and discourse studies and an interdisciplinary field of mainly qualitative inquiry which considers language use as social practice and investigates the role and function of discourse, i.e. language use, in social relations, social change, power and ideology; as well as the way these factors affect it. "Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is "a theory and method analyzing the way that individuals and institutions use language" (Richardson, 2007; quoted by Majdedin, Taghinezhad & Nabizadeh, 2014, p 238).

Discourse, text and language use as well as their different elements such as genre, style, tone, word choice and other communicative and semiotic aspects all have a reciprocal and bilateral relationship with the social context, social situation, social relations and the social practice. Discourse and language use are affected and formed by the social phenomena, but also build and influence the social phenomena. (Fairclough, 2010)

Conversation Analysis (CA) is a methodological approach and scope of inquiry in linguistic research which investigates and analyzes the pragmatic,

communicative, social, semantic and rhetorical aspects and characteristics of conversations. It surveys and studies the manner of interaction between the participants of conversation and discusses the transaction of messages and meaning in the conversation (Johnstone, 2008; Gee, 2013; Richards & Schmidt, 2010).

Fairclough (1993, 1995a) uses the concept "*discourse*" with three different meanings. In its most abstract meaning or sense, the term discourse refers to language use as social practice. In this regard, discourse is both the creator and the product of other phenomena. The second meaning of the word discourse is a type of language usage in a particular scope, as in the phrases "political discourse" or "scientific discourse". The third use of the concept of discourse is, in connection to, and in association with, systems of beliefs, schools of thoughts, ideological systems and distinct political ideas. In this sense, the word discourse is a count noun (as in "*a discourse*", "*that discourse*", "*those discourses*", etc.) This application of the word discourse refers to a way or method of speech that grants meaning to the experiences coming from a specific viewpoint. In this sense, the term discourse refers to any discourse that is separable and distinguishable from other discourses, such as neoliberalist discourse, Marxist discourse, consumer discourse, conservationist discourse or environmentalist discourse.

According to Fairclough (1995b), discourse contributes in developing and building social identity, social relations and systems of knowledge, meaning and beliefs, hence having three functions: identity function, relational function and ideational function.

Fairclough (1992b) points out that, social structures, power relations, social and cultural processes and social relations, are linked to, and influenced by, discourse practice. Fairclough highlights the complex relationship between discourse practice and social structures, which is changed over time within cultural and historic contexts. Discourse as social practice, affects and influences social relations and structures. It builds the social phenomena and is simultaneously produced by them. Social structures and power relations shape and form social practices, and discourse is a social practice intrinsically and inherently. Investigating and understanding the relationship and link between

discourse or text and sociocultural structures and processes requires an interdisciplinary approach which combines discourse analysis and social analysis, therefore, text analysis alone cannot provide insight about the dynamic relationship between discourse and social structures (Fairclough, 1992b, 2001a&b, 2002 & 2003).

Fairclough's three-dimensional model, provides a methodological and theoretical framework for conducting and implementing critical discourse analysis, in which, the three dimensions of analysis are, first, the text and its characteristics, second, discourse practice and the process of production and consumption of text, and finally, social practice. This model is an analytical framework for empirical studies about communication and society. It provides three layers for examining the textual, discursive and social characteristics of language use for the purpose of identifying the link and relationship between discourse as language use and social practice on one side, and social structures, relations and interactions, on the other (Yarmohammadi, 2014; Handerson, 2005).

In any study aiming to conduct critical discourse analysis, two aspects of discourse are of critical importance, one, the communicative event, and two, the discursive order. The former is an instance of language use, while the latter is the genre and the possible, relevant and appropriate discursive practices within a social institution, establishment, environment or field (Yarmohammadi, 2014a&b).

A conversation is a communicative event and a situation of language use in which two or several parties or participants exchange meanings, ideas and messages verbally, i.e. through speaking and talking (or sign language), in order to communicate, cooperate, collaborate and do things or to share mental ideas and concepts. A conversation is subject to rules known as conversational maxims or conversational implicatures and occurs within a particular sociolinguistic, pragmatic and cultural context. A conversation is a social activity and a system of interaction, exchange and building relationship which is a purposeful act of modifying and utilizing social relations and involves elements and aspects relevant to social position, power and social role, and therefore, can be subject to application of critical analysis.

Conversations are bilateral or multilateral communicative speech events, and involve organized language use in form of purposeful and collaborative speaking and linguistic interaction (Sze, 1995). An important part of daily language use and linguistic communication is done through conversations and most instances of daily speaking involve engaging in different forms of conversations. To be able to communicate in a particular language and the ability to speak a certain language both are considered identical and equal to being able to have a conversation in that language. The majority of speech events in different social contexts and situations of daily life are conversations and many speech acts are done within and by, conversations (Stans et al, 2018; Mengis & Eppler, 2008; Koester, 2002; Colombetti, 2000; & Cicourel, 1979).

Conversation practice and acquiring the ability to make conversations are vitally critical in development of speaking skill. In second and foreign language learning, learning how to hold conversations is essential to gain speaking ability. Conversation practice plays an important role in development of communicative competence and speaking skill (Cowley, 2019; Paisley, 2019; Johnson, 2016; Cazden, 2005; Hall & Verplaetse, 2000).

Many approaches and methods of language teaching either rely on, or pay central attention to, and have emphatic focus on, textbooks as sources and facilitators of language learning (Tomlinson, 2016; Gak, 2011).

In any education system, all components, such as curricula, syllabus and textbooks are influenced and affected by social, cultural and ideological factors. Educational policies and regulations which govern compiling and developing the textbooks are designed based on a wide range of sociocultural and ideological values, which together form and construct the education system (Dang & Seals, 2018; Curdt-Christiansen & Weninger, 2015; Kumar, 1988). The intrinsic, inherent and unavoidable presence and effects of sociocultural and ideological values in the components of education systems, justify and demand the application of methods of critical discourse analysis for inquiring and investigation their different aspects and elements, aiming quality improvement and ensuring equal opportunities within the education system (Rogers, 2011).

The goal of this thesis is to conduct a critical discourse analysis of instructional conversations of Vision 3 textbook based on Fairclough's three-dimensional model which investigates the sociocultural and ideological aspects of discursive and social practice within the textbook conversations. This study critically analyzes the written conversations which are educational samples provided and presented for the purpose of teaching and fostering speaking skill and language use ability in conversations. Even though textbook conversations are reproduced and practiced in classroom settings as a learning activity, analysis of written unreal conversations (i. e, not in real situations or between real people) puts this study in the category of text linguistics, rather than conversation analysis.

The aim of this thesis is to apply Fairclough's model of *Critical Discourse Analysis* (CDA) to *Conversation Analysis* (CA) of the six educational conversations in the Iranian textbook *Vision 3* with discussion of possible pedagogical implications for English language teaching in school classes.

Fairclough's three-dimensional model for critical discourse analysis provides a framework for critical analysis of discourse as social practice and in relation to power, ideology and social relations. The three dimensions or aspects of critical discourse analysis in Fairclough's model are text, discursive practice and social practice. Discourse, is analyzed and surveyed with regard to its language characteristics and linguistic properties in the first dimension. The second dimension, discursive practice, encompasses the processes of production, distribution and consumption of discourse as language use within a specific social context. The third dimension, social practice, entails the discourse order and the functional role of discourse as an active element modifying, maintaining or establishing social relations (Janks, 1997).

Fairclough's model has attracted special attention from researchers conducting studies with scopes and domains relevant to communication and social sciences as a sociolinguistic model connecting and relating discourse as language use with social change, social relations and ideology. Education, both as a process and a phenomenon, is social by nature. Education requires communicative interaction, is value-bound due to the necessity of acts of selection and decision-making in its different stages and involves use of some kind of sign system for

transferring meaning and knowledge. Policy-making in education and the process of education both constitute its social essence. Language teaching as a component of education and a form of educational activity is a social issue and involves interaction within groups, requires communication and includes choices, viewpoints and values which all build its social essence. Conversation, as a form of communication and social interaction and a kind of language use in context, has important socio-communicative aspects which can be subjects of critical discourse analysis. Educational sample conversations within language textbooks, both independently and as parts of the textbooks, retain social and context-specific communicative features and characteristics, and portray the ideology and intended sociolinguistic and cultural properties of the textbooks, syllabi, curricula and education systems.

In recent years, there has been a substantial and significant number of studies using Fairclough's model for critically analyzing textbooks or their certain characteristics and aspects such as ideology, gender view, etc., mainly exploring the textbooks as a whole with their all parts and sections, yet investigating certain predefined factors. While the present study also uses Fairclough's three-dimensional model as its framework, it focuses on the parts of Vision 3 textbook which contain conversations and attempts to integrate Fairclough's model of critical discourse analysis to conversation analysis of educational conversations.

This thesis aims and attempts to adapt critical discourse analysis approach and Fairclough's three-dimensional model to critically analyze the conversations presented in Vision 3 textbook. This involves an eclectic methodological overlap between critical discourse analysis, discourse analysis, text linguistics and conversation analysis to take a critical stand about different aspects of Vision 3 conversations.

The present study was planned to be developed upon the critical discourse analysis (CDA) of the conversations parts of the Iranian Ministry of Education's *Vision 3* English language textbook based on the newer version of Norman Fairclough's model of critical discourse analysis. This new version is mainly reflected in the 2001 edition of *Language and Power* and the 2003 book *Analysing Discourse: Textual Analysis for Social Research*, as well as the 2010

edition of Fairclough's book *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. The model is also called Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model and the title "Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model" is also famous and widespread, though the new version of the model used in this study will also include the 2003 revisions. In this study, the author has attempted to include more recent ideas of Fairclough in critical discourse analysis as a framework. The main focus of the study is ideology and sociocultural values and their presentation or expression in the conversation parts of *Vision 3* textbook. The study aims to find, analyze and discuss the elements of the presented ideology in conversation parts. The study also seeks to survey the practical pedagogical and instructional aspects of critical discourse analysis of ideology and sociocultural values in conversation sections of Iranian 12th grade textbook, and attempts to provide classroom advice for teaching English, especially within schools' teaching contexts based on the findings of the critical discourse analysis of ideology and sociocultural values in conversations.

Critical discourse analysis (CDA) is an interdisciplinary, or as Norman Fairclough (2003) calls it "*transdisciplinary*" field exploring the connection and relationship between *language*, *power* and *ideology* while the last one (ideology) constitutes the right to exercise the second one and acts as a set of assumptions which legitimizes the difference in power and the distribution of power in existing social relations. CDA views discourse, text and speech as *practice* and *social process* which forms the foundation of social relations, social actions and *social change* (Fairclough, 1989; 1995 & 2003; van Dijk, 1998; Wodak, 2001a&b).

Conversation parts in language textbooks are one of the most communicative areas of textbook-based language learning programs and are also context-specific and situation-based and are important in building communicative competence. Also, education systems are all ideology-based and ideology-bound and therefore, supportive of some certain ideology (Tham, 2013; Ansell and Lindvall, 2013; Fiala, 2007; Davidson, 2017). What variety of language to teach, language policy and political issues are all influential in all textbook materials, including conversation parts (Arzoz, 2007; Van der Jeught, 2015; Ogunsiyi, 2015). Moreover, language and culture are inseparable, yet some education systems

attempt to present language without its culture or try to manipulate the original culture or what cultural knowledge students learn. On the other hand, "textbooks are the core of any language program." (Sheldon, 1988) and are of great importance (Richards, 2001) in formal language teaching. Discourse has psychological effect, among other types of impact and the emotional and psychological content of discourse affects cognition and therefore, language comprehension and language processing (Jiménez-Ortega et al, 2012). The underlying ideology of the education system and the ideology that curriculum designers, policy-makers and textbook developers follow, affect the content compilation and the content selection in developing the textbooks (Hu, 2005; Curdt-Christiansen & Weninger, 2015; Phyak, 2016; Ricento & Hornberger, 1996; Luke, 1988; Connelly & Connelly, 2012, Hu & Adamson, 2012; Adamson & Morris, 2014 & Spring, 2011). Considering all these facts and having all these in mind, it can be inferred that ideology and discourse in textbook's pedagogical settings are important in teaching process and evaluating the book as appropriate or inappropriate. In addition, the way ideology is dealt with in a textbook affects the discourse in its different parts, especially conversation parts and therefore, affects students learning. These all have pedagogical and instructional importance and can potentially be the topic of useful advice for classroom activity, teaching and pedagogy in practice.

Teaching conversation is of critical and crucial importance in teaching the speaking skill. Speaking is one the major skills of language and is the most widely-used skill in daily life communication. Many people, who choose or need to learn a foreign language, decide to learn the language mainly for being able to speak that language (Leong & Ahmadi, 2017; Mulyati, 2013; Bahrani & Soltani, 2012; Aliakbari & Jamalvandi, 2010; Egan, 1999).

Instructive and instructional conversations within language learning textbooks are among the main materials used in the classroom and the teaching-learning process (Savova, 2018; Donato, 2000). These readymade pre-planned conversations are designed and developed with focus on the aims and objectives of the lesson, syllabus and the curriculum (Savova, 2018; Saunders & Goldenberg, 2017; Chernova & Mustafina, 2016; Dahmardeh; 2009; Berry &

Englert, 2005; Gilmore, 2004; Donato, 2000). The content, scenario, context and situation are all manipulated, affected and influenced by the author(s) who themselves are impressed and directed by the educational policies, curriculum, syllabus and other components of the education system (Erling & Seargeant, 2013; Shamim, 2008; Paulston & Heidemann, 2006; Nunan, 2003; Chern, 2002; Adley-SantaMaria, 1997 & Kumar, 1986).

1.2 Research Assumptions

Textbooks are not neutral means or instruments of transferring knowledge. The education systems, curricula and the textbooks are all highly influenced by ideology (Hodge & Kress, 1993; van Dijk, 2004; Howard & Dedo, 1989). Language is not only words and grammar; it is rather a communicative system within the society that people use to share ideas, beliefs and thoughts (Koosha et al, 2004). Culture and ideology are reflected, and are present in textbooks (Sajid, 2015).

The ideological bases and foundations of any education system are portrayed and depicted in the textbooks used in that education system. Ideology and sociocultural factors affect the content and form in textbooks and other learning materials (Curdt-Christiansen & Weninger, 2015; Ping, 2015).

Critical discourse analysis investigates and quests the dynamic, complex, two-sided and bilateral relationship between the use of language (discourse) and power, ideology, social relations, social structures, power relations and inequality. It examines the processes through which discourse and social or political phenomena dialectically affect and influence one another (Karimian Sichani, 2015; Banta, 2012).

Based on available literature and preceding similar studies, it is assumed that Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model's factors and parameters can be effectively applied to the content and structure of the conversation parts of the *Vision 3* textbook to reveal the elements of ideology and sociocultural values behind *Vision 3* textbook and the underlying aspects of ideological foundations of *Vision 3* (Roohani & Heidarian, 2012).

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the discourse elements of the conversations of Iranian textbook *Vision 3*, the 12th grade English language for Iranian high schools, based on Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model?
2. What are the social, ideological and sociocultural dimensions of the discourse within conversations in *Vision 3* textbook?
3. What are the teaching implications of critical discourse analysis applied on the conversation sections of *Vision 3* textbook?

1.4 Definition and Explanation of Key Terms

Critical Discourse Analysis

Critical discourse analysis (CDA) is an interdisciplinary approach of studying spoken or written discourse that considers language as a form of social practice or action which is interrelated to social relations and power. It is general argument in CDA that non-linguistic social practice and linguistic practice constitute one another. CDA researchers focus on discovering and investigating how societal relations of power are established, maintained and reinforced through the use of language in different contexts and situations (Fairclough, 1995). The difference between CDA and discourse analysis is that the former deals with, and investigates, concepts such as power, ideology, social relations and social inequalities derived from discourse and its different aspects (Blommaert & Bucean, 2000).

Muhamad Aqeel et al (2015) define critical discourse analysis as following:

"It is a branch of Applied Linguistics and as a field fall[ing] within the group of "Humanities" and "Social Science". CDA or CDS is a form of Discourse Analysis, through which we study the relationship between discourse and ideology (consisting set of beliefs, behaviors and attitudes)."

Based on Sheyholislami's (2009) quotation from van Dijk and Fairclough, the definition of CDA is as following:

"According to van Dijk (1998a), Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a field that is concerned with studying and analyzing written and spoken texts to reveal the discursive sources of power, dominance, inequality and bias. It examines how these discursive sources are maintained and reproduced within specific social, political and historical contexts. In a similar vein, Fairclough (1993) defines CDA as discourse analysis which aims to systematically explore often opaque relationships of causality and determination between (a) discursive practices, events and texts, and (b) wider social and cultural structures, relations and processes; to investigate how such practices, events and texts arise out of and are ideologically shaped by relations of power and struggles over power; and to explore how the opacity of these relationships between discourse and society is itself a factor securing power and hegemony."

According to Karimian Sichani and Hadian (2015), "Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a branch of applied linguistics which studies discourse and language in relation to social and political issues to discover how they affect each other". (Karimian & Hadian, 2015, p. 66)

Fairclough (2012), defines CDA as "... a branch of critical social analysis, which contributes to the latter a focus on discourse and on relations between discourse and other social elements (e.g. on how discourse figures in ideologies and power relations)."

Critical Discourse Analysis is an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary field within the domain of applied linguistics and critical social studies, which studies the way language use (discourse), and the social practice and society are conditioned by each other (Fairclough & Chouliaraki, 1999; Fairclough, 2003 & 2012; Banta, 2012). CDA analyzes how language is used to form, reproduce, maintain and justify power, power relations, societal relations and social structures, and how these four form, shape, affect and influence language use. CDA explores the dialectical two-sided relationship between discourse and language use, and ideology, power, power relations, social structures and societal relations; asserting and emphasizing power, ideology and social practice are

interrelated and interwoven to language use (Fairclough, 1989, 2001, 2003 & 2010).

Richards and Schmidt (2010), in their *Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, defined critical discourse analysis as "a form of discourse analysis that takes a critical stance towards how language is used and analyzes texts and other discourse types in order to identify the ideology and values underlying them. It seeks to reveal the interests and power relations in any institutional and socio-historical context through analysing the ways that people use language." (Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics, 2010, p. 145).

Textbook

According to Richards & Schmidt (2010, p. 595), a textbook is "a book on a specific subject used as a teaching/learning guide, especially in a school or college. Textbooks for foreign language learning are often part of a graded series covering multiple skills (listening, reading, writing, speaking, grammar) or deal with a single skill (e.g. reading)."

Conversation

A conversation is a situation where two or more participants use verbal (oral) language to interact and exchange ideas. A conversation is an instance of a communicative event and a communicative context in which people *talk* or *speak* to one another in order to communicate, interact and share ideas, engage in speech acts, demand certain reactions or influence the other party or participant (Sze, 1995).

1.5 Statement of the Problem

There are systems of ideology behind language learning textbooks and their learning materials. Textbooks of different education systems have different ideological roots (Padilla & Vana, 2019; Akkaymak, 2015; Samadikhah & Shahrokhi, 2015). According to Foucault, "No text is ideologically innocent" (Foucault, 1971, quoted in Sheridan Smith, 1972, p. 215), and textbooks are no exception. In any curriculum, there is some *curriculum ideology* which philosophically justifies the goals, objectives, educational programmes and

instruction methods, hence building and constructing a foundation or base for the curriculum, the education system and its components (Richards & Schmidt, 2010; Fiala, 2007; Cantoni, et al, 2007; Inglis, 1974; Breidlid, 2003; Goodson, 1990). Not many studies have surveyed discourse of Iranian English textbooks and its discursive practice, social practice and ideology in details and comprehensively. In fact, few studies have developed a full and complete systematic big picture of the socio-discursive practice and ideology of Iranian textbooks. Teachers and students often do not pay attention to the underlying ideology of the textbooks and ignore them. Teaching and instructing processes involve some neglect of the ideological aspects of the textbooks.

Two important issues in critical discourse studies are ideology and sociocultural values (Fairclough, 1995).

Ideology is a system of general ideas, beliefs, doctrines and concepts which builds and constructs the foundation and basis of an educational system (Richards & Schmidt, 2010). According to Richards and Schmidt (2010), "the relationships between ideology, language, and discourse are a central focus of critical theory and critical linguistics." (Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics, 2010, p 269).

It is obvious and clear that ideology is much more than gender representation or mere social relations which are the main focus of most similar studies. Ideology is a complex and complicated large system beyond only gender equality or gender discrimination. In fact, ideology deeply and dramatically affects many pedagogic aspects such as material choice, design of conversation scenario, emphasis or negligence towards certain cultural and even linguistic-structural features of language, etc. and is therefore worthy of investigation and attention. A search of academic search engines and databases such as *Google Scholar*, *ERIC* and *ScinceDirect* shows that Iranian textbooks before and after the recent curriculum reform have been subject of very few cases of ideology and conversation analysis and the topic and scope of ideology within school textbooks of the national education system, in general, and *Vision 3*, in particular, remains a new and relatively unexamined territory. *Vision 3* textbook was released and entered Iran's third-grade high school classes in September 2018 and is a new

textbook, and therefore, few studies have been done on it. There are a lot of studies focusing on gender representation and gender bias, but ideology of textbooks has been the subject of much fewer studies (Tao Xiong & Yamin Qian, 2012).

Values are general and abstract notions or ideas of determining and judging what is important or good. They are concepts, generalizable thoughts, beliefs or intellectual and mental images of criteria for identifying and recognizing an action or idea as appropriate and right. Values reveal and determine what "should" or "ought to" be, and reflect and portray the ideal or perfect status (Zimmerman, 2002; Schroeder, 2008).

In any culture and society, there are general values which affect and regulate behavioural norms and actions. These values are public notions of importance and appropriateness. Sociocultural values are related to social, cultural and behavioural norms, but are more general and more intellectually or mentally complex than norms (Brentano, 1969; Ross, 1930; Ritov & Baron, 1999; Baron & Ritov, 2009; Baron & Spranca, 1997).

Practicing conversations is one of the most important categories of tasks and activities essential for teaching speaking (Burns, 2019). Conversation activities and exercises are critically necessary in the process of developing the speaking skill (Burns, 1998; Bailey, 2003; Goh & Burns, 2012). The authenticity, originality and communicative potentials of instructive and instructional conversations of textbooks, as well as the rich language of their content, determine the effectiveness and efficacy of these conversation samples (Cane, 1998; Bailey & Savage, 1994; Sayer, 2005). Carefully designed sample conversations provide useful and beneficial opportunities for guided practice. Instructive and instructional conversations which are sources of meaningful and rich input help develop effective speaking skills and communicative ability (Herlina & Holandiyah, 2015; Bardovi-Harling et al, 1991; Hughes & Reed, 2016; Kürüm, 2016). Guided sample conversations can be used for role-play and controlled practice as well as free practice using the patterns, words, phrases, sentences and expressions provided. Textbook conversations are one of the most widely available and main sources of instructive and instructional conversations

(Hussain, 2017; Aleksandrzak, 2011; Richards, 2006; Gudu, 2015). In order for textbooks' instructive and instructional conversations to be effective and successful for the purpose of improving the speaking skill and enhancing the communicative abilities, the content, scenario, presented context and the portrayed communicative situation should be thoroughly and meticulously considered when and before the sample conversations are composed and compiled (Ahmed et al, 2015; Hanifa, 2018; Faucette, 2001). Successful instructional use of sample conversations in tasks and activities such as role-playing and oral reproduction depends to a high extent on the content and context presented in the conversations (Krebt, 2017; Rahman, 2010; Leong & Ahmadi, 2017).

Considering and having in mind the importance and requirements of textbooks' instructional conversations as well as the influence of the educational system and curriculum ideology in content development and content selection, an investigation with CDA approach can help evaluate and potentially revise the textbook conversations. A CDA inquiry can help with identification and analysis of the impact of textbook's underlying ideology on design and development of the sample conversations of the textbook.

1. 6 Significance of the Study

Effective and proper teaching and successful instruction require classroom activity that encourages and involves critical thinking, critical awareness, creativity and consciousness of intertextual, intratextual and hypertextual relations of texts as well as their hidden and obvious ideological intentions. Teachers need ideological awareness to provide ideological consciousness to the learners and to include and embed critical use of texts in their teaching and pedagogy.

It is important that teachers be given deep understanding of the ideology of the textbooks they teach. Familiarizing the teachers with the considerations, expectations and intentions of the textbook developers can help teachers teach more effectively and to maintain some kind of balance between the rich language teaching responsibility and the ideological considerations of the education system. Also, choosing appropriate supplementary activities and materials requires

understanding the ideology of the textbooks; otherwise, the lack of harmony will confuse the learners. The same is true about choosing the teaching method.

Teachers should understand the ideology within the content of textbooks for providing effective education (Apple, 2000). This establishes the importance of understanding textbooks' ideology for teachers to act as effective educators.

Teaching conversation vastly contributes to facilitating the development of speaking skill and communicative competence (Shumin, 2002; Walsh, 2002 & Luo, 2013). Due to the importance of the development of speaking skill and communicative competence as two of the major goals of language teaching and learning, it is important to adapt and employ appropriate teaching methods, strategies, techniques and tactics to efficiently teach conversation skills as prerequisite of speaking skill and communicative competence. As the ideological bases and foundations of the education system, curriculum, syllabus, educational context and the instructional content profoundly affect the teaching methods, the process of instruction and the requirements for success of the teacher's instruction, attempts to identify and analyze the ideology behind the components of the education system and instruction process and to raise awareness about the impact of ideology on teaching methods and classroom decision-making, seem to be worthwhile (Apple, 2019; Eisner, 2002).

The ideology with and behind each of the components of the education system and the instruction process, influences and affects the way teachers teach, what happens in the classroom and what and how the learners learn, therefore, awareness and understanding of ideological aspects of the elements of the education system, including the instructional content would be helpful to both the teachers and the learners (Kiraz & Ozdemir, 2006; Simmie & Edling, 2016; Walmsley, 1981; King, 1991; Giroux, 1981 & McGroarty, 2010).

1.7 Thesis Organization

The contents of this thesis are arranged and presented in five chapters. Chapter one covers the introduction of topic, general view, research assumptions, research questions, statement of the problem, the significance of the study and the definition of the key terms. The second chapter contains the theoretical

foundations, the review of literature, and the fundamental concepts and some of the related empirical studies as samples of the preceding studies. The third chapter entails methodology, research materials, procedures and data analysis. The fourth chapter is about the study's findings, results, discussion and conclusion of the study. The final chapter, chapter five, includes the summary of the main findings, pedagogical and instructional implications, practical advice for teaching and classroom activity and suggestions for further studies.

Chapter Two

Review of the Literature

2.1 Theoretical Foundations

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a qualitative analytical interdisciplinary approach to studying *discourse as language use* and its dynamic, dialectical and bilateral links and connections with social relations, power and ideology. CDA explores and studies the relationship between the use of language within different contexts and in various genres, and the way it affects, and is affected by, social relations, power relations, ideology and instances of injustice, inequality, discrimination and control (Abdul Jabar & Yunus, 2017; Reagan, 2006; Wodak & Chilton, 2005; van Dijk, 1993; 1995).

CDA reveals and extracts both the implicit and explicit relationships between *language use* and *ideology, power, social relations* and *social interactions* and *practices*, whether these relationships are hidden (opaque) or obvious (transparent) (Amerian & Esmaili, 2014). A major difference that distinguishes between discourse analysis (DA) and CDA, is that description of text and discourse is done in CDA as the surface level and the superficial layer of the analysis. The critical core of CDA is finding the role of language and language use in social links and relationships and the way power is exercised and implicated within the society, as well as the processes of "naturalization, internalization and transfer of ideology", social control and sociocultural change (Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 1999; Fairclough & Wodak, 1997, Fairclough, 1992, 1993 & 1995a&b). A CDA study is expected to help with social reform, or at least raising awareness about using language for creation and stabilization of power (Reagan, 2006).

Fairclough (1995b:14) believes "ideology is meaning serving power" and discourse is "language use as social practice". He believes in existence of a dialectical relationship between communicative event and discourse order. Fairclough argues that there is a complex and deep relationship between text (discourse) and social structures and processes and social structures and power relations shape the social practices through language use, hence there is need for

integration and combination of text analysis and social analysis (Yarmohammadi, 2014a&b).

A major linguistic theory widely used and adopted as the theoretical foundation and systematic base for notable critical discourse analysis researchers and authors has been Michael Halliday's 1985 Systematic Functional Grammar which provides a semiotic and semantic analysis of grammar and linguistic output in which, different linguistic descriptions of realities (phenomena) are related to different constructions of them and linguistic structures function ideationally. This offers a linguistic theoretical ground for classifying the social actor types semiotic system in CDA. Critical semiotics, a main theoretical and analytical base in CDA studies is derived from Halliday's SFG (Tenorio, 2011; Fairclough, 1995a&b & 2010).

2.2 Review of the Literature

Applying discourse analysis and critical discourse analysis to English language textbooks or their specific parts and aspects has been common in recent years. Social aspects such as ideology, religion, sexual discrimination, gender representation, political ideas and ethnical or racial issues have been some of the topics of critical discourse analysis of English language textbooks, though gender representation and other gender-related topics have been the target of far more attention.

Mojavezi and Aslani (2017) conducted CDA on conversation parts of Headway 2 textbook based on Fairclough's 1989 model using frequency measurement of the concepts and concluded that "*interpersonal and introspective had the highest rank regarding content in this textbook*" (Mojavezi & Aslani, 2017, p. 27).

Esmaili and Amerian (2014) analyzed gender representation in Iranian schools' English textbooks and the results revealed that in compliance with the Iranian culture, the books presented a sexist view against women and ideological sexual discrimination was observed in the textbooks. Moreover, this study applied Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model to American Headway English

language textbooks and concluded that they depicted and portrayed a sexist representation or manifestation of female gender in "covert" and "overt" ways and that they showed both obvious and unobvious sexist attitude and discrimination against women, the unobvious one being the exploitation of women for "selling". Esmaili and Amerian believe that this sexist and discriminative view was a sign of capitalistic economic ideology behind the textbooks.

Jeddi Kazerooni and Tabatabaei (2017) published a paper titled "Textbook Evaluation: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Talk Time Series" with focus on gender presence and friendship relationships using Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model. Jeddi Kazerooni and Tabatabaei maintain that the Talk Time textbook series showed equal presence of both male and female genders. According to Jeddi Kazerooni and Tabatabaei, there was no sexism in Talk Time series.

Ahmad Nadhif (2017) analyzed the presence of moral and religious values in Indonesian high school English textbooks using Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model and found several aspects of Western values and various dimensions of Western-Secular ideology within the textbook.

Beiki and Gharaguzlu (2017) used Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model to analyze gender representation and gender roles as well as social relations of genders and subject positions in *American English File* textbooks series. They point out that the series contained equal presence of male and female characters and that the social occupational roles for females were having jobs such as doctor, teacher, nurse, etc. and jobs requiring physical strength for males. Beiki and Gharaguzlu also categorized the subject positions and produced numerical data such as percentage of same or opposite sex relationships, frequency of presence of genders, etc.

Roohani and Heidari's 2012 paper titled "Evaluating an Instructional Textbook: A Critical Discourse Perspective" analyzed the gender representation, gender roles and gender bias in Summit 2B textbook and concluded that though there is equal presence of both male and female genders, the authors have not made much effort to eliminate gender biases. Also, although gender presence was

equal, personality adjectives and characteristics were not equally distributed between the two genders.

Roohani and Tanbakooei (2012) used Fairclough's 1989 model to analyze Passage 1 and First Certificate textbooks' vocabulary and grammar parts. The results showed that in both textbooks the social relations, social status and power were equal between males and females and that the dominant social relation in Passage 1 was friends, while the First Certificate favoured TV reporter as the dominant social relation. Authors believe that Passage 1 focuses on uncontroversial issues, while First Certificate pays more attention to controversial issues.

Cahl (2016) used Fairclough's 1989 model to apply CDA to South African schools' English language textbook of the 8th grade. He concluded conservative ideas were almost dominant within the textbook, and that many exercises were undemanding and easy, leading students to previously intended answers, a characteristics that damages critical thinking and creativity. He also found gender bias in the textbook.

Hamdan Alghamdi (2018) discusses and argues against very strong presence of American lifestyle and culture in two popular English language textbooks, believing the huge "gap" between students' culture and lifestyle and the unfamiliar Western lifestyle and culture presented in the textbooks makes teachers have to spend a lot of time explaining topics and causes the students to become confused.

Al-Kayed et al (2020) used Fairclough's 1995 three-dimensional framework to conduct a CDA study on gender representation in Interchange 1A and 2B textbooks. Analysis of roles, activities and visibility revealed that although the textbook contents were biased in favour of men in certain roles and activities and some imbalance existed in specific areas of social or occupational activity between men and women, the pictorial representation, visibility and social status were equal in the textbooks.

Amerian and Esmaeeli (2015) report there has been a large body of publications and literature about using critical discourse analysis to investigate

gender representation, gender bias and sexism in language textbooks. Most publications confirm existence of gender bias and sexism in different textbooks.

Tahriri and Moradpour (2014) explored the Top Notch Series regarding gender representation using a Critical Discourse Analysis model. For this purpose, they investigated three major aspects of gender, i.e. relations, positions, and content based on Fairclough's (2001) three-dimensional model. The findings revealed that both genders are represented nearly equally. This study also showed that the series has acted based on the capitalistic ideology in representing gender.

Keshavarz and Malek (2009) studied gender representation in the ILI (Iran Language Institute) and True to Life textbooks concerning social relations, subject positions and contents. This study revealed that these two textbooks series represent equal social status between characters of both male and female gender. Moreover, dominant themes in these two series were friends, occupational and commercial positions. Also, representation of western economy and capitalism was significant in the both series.

Stockdale (2006, cited in Roohani & Tanbakooei, 2012) conducted an evaluation of Impact Values series in relevance to gender representation using Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model. He investigated this series regarding issues related to gender bias, including visibility, firstness, nouns, pronouns and discourse roles. The study revealed that the series showed substantial bias favoring to males.

Ansary and Babaii (2003), performed a critical discourse analysis study to analyze sexism in Right Path to English I and Right Path to English II Iranian textbooks. Their results of the study showed that the two textbooks retain characteristics of a sexist text

Amal Saleh, Sajjadi, and Yarmohammadi (2006) examined the contents of Iranian EFL high school textbooks. They reported the textbooks ignored female gender. It was also revealed that traditional and stereotypical roles were assigned and attributed to females.

Sahragard and Davatgarzadeh (2010) applied a critical discourse approach to analyze the linguistic representation of male and female social actors, social roles and formation of gender identities in the contents of New Interchange series.

The results showed that in the contents of the series textbooks, female characters were represented as active, independent, well-spoken, confident and even sometimes more important.

Gonzalez (2011) carried out a CDA study on Mexican schools EFL textbooks. The findings and results revealed that the contents of textbooks were inauthentic. Attributing traditional domestic and social roles was also reported.

Majdedin et al (2014) utilized Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model to conduct critical discourse analysis for investigation of *subject positions, social relations, and contents* of 24 textbooks used at two famous language institutions in Shiraz, Iran. The results showed that Western culture dominated the contents of the textbooks ideologically and culturally. Presence of Western values, consumerism and commerce-related topics was observed. Findings also revealed that sports, friendship, travelling and commerce were predominant topics and themes in the contents of the analyzed textbooks.

Tao Xiong & Yamin Qian (2012), in an article titled "Ideologies of English in a Chinese High School EFL Textbook: A Critical Discourse Analysis" studied the ideological aspects of English language teaching in today's China, focusing specifically on textbook discourse. They constituted their research framework based on critical theories of language and education, applying critical discourse analysis as a methodological approach identified and characterized by "a socially committed attitude" in text interpretation and explanation (Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 75). Their study on the ideological dimensions presented by the textbooks, resulted in finding evidence of "selective representation of the history of English", "shallow sociolinguistic explanations, and "grammatical prescriptivism". They believed the aforementioned characteristics and issues which they made evident, were due to the "Anglo-centric" ideological system of language which assumes the sociolinguistic "neutrality" and grammatical "uniformity" of English (Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 75). They suggested a multicultural and cosmopolitan approach and attitude towards curriculum development characterized by an intercultural understanding of both the local and the global aspects of ideology, culture and viewpoint (Xiong & Qian, 2012).

Xiong & Qian (2012) highlight "an ongoing ideological debate on dominant languages and varieties in the literature", citing Blommaert (1999), Kubota (1998), Milroy (2001) and Seargeant (2008) as examples. According to Xiong & Qian (2012), the ideological intentions in school textbooks has been among the key research themes, as a result of what they believe is an "axiomatic connection between education and politics" in China after 1949 (Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76). They point out that some of the earlier studies of the topic are the works of Ridley, Godwin and Doolin (1971), Sproul (1979), and Kwong (1985).

Xiong & Qian (2012) reported that the exact topic of English in China has been explored from aspects, and in areas, such as comparative education, sociolinguistics and applied linguistics. According to Xiong & Qian (2012), in 2004, Adamson conducted a comprehensive study of the issue of curriculum from a historical and comparative aspect. You (2010, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012) conducted another longitudinal study of teaching English language in China specifically emphasizing on writing instruction.

Critical discourse analysis (CDA), "an interdisciplinary methodological approach" to issues of language, society, power and inequality, constituted by a commitment to generating critical awareness about the aforementioned issues with a "socially emancipating agenda", has been growingly used by education researchers internationally to study and analyze educational problems (Gee, 1999, 2008, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76; Rogers, 2008, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76). Some of the examples of applying CDA to explore educational issues in educational literature according to Xiong & Qian (2012) include Barnard's 2003 study investigating how responsibility for war was "minimized in Japanese high school history textbooks", as well as the study by De los Heros in 2009 with CDA approach, surveying the ideological aspects related to linguistic prescriptivism in Peru's official language textbook for the students of the first grade of high school (Xiong & Qian, 2012).

Liu (2005a, 2005b, 2005c) used the critical discourse analysis paradigm for critically analyzing Chinese language textbooks in relation to the discursive construction of cultural knowledge and values. He suggested further studies which could "critically analyze and demystify the discourses constructed in the

textbooks” and considered this critical awareness to be the “most important aspect of a literacy that enables children to read the world” (Liu, 2005a, p. 319).

Curdt-Christiansen (2008, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012) investigated and explored the cultural themes of the texts used in a Chinese heritage language school in Montreal. The author investigated the texts and demonstrated how they educated and socialized the students through forming their worldview.

Xiong & Qian (2012) believe that, despite the recent growth in critical approach to Chinese school textbooks, the textbooks for English language teaching (ELT) in China have been the target and focus of relatively less attention. You (2005, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012) in an article titled "Ideology, Textbooks, and the Rhetoric of Production in China", applied a widely critical approach with a CDA perspective generated from Marxist principles on ideology and a contrastive rhetoric approach. You conducted an important study "of the two editions of a composition textbook that contributes towards a rhetoric for textbook production in China" (Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76).

Chen (2010, cited in Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76) performed an analysis of "the semiotic construal of attitudinal curriculum goals in English as a foreign language (EFL) textbooks" to find out "how multimodal discourses orient values in texts".

Yu and Huang (2008) reviewed the studies on Chinese primary and secondary English textbooks published in a period of 27 years from 1980 to 2007, noticing a "promotional tendency" in the textbooks evaluation. They called for "more rigorous research" (Xiong & Qian, 2012, p. 76).

According to Xiong and Qian (2012), the topic of language ideology in EFL textbooks has not been addressed thoroughly and comprehensively enough, and has not been explicitly and adequately investigated.

To further investigate and explore the ideological aspects of English language presentation and depiction in Chinese textbooks, Xiong and Qian (2012) aimed to deal with the issue of English ideologies using a "CDA-informed approach" (Xiong and Qian, 2012, p. 76). They inquired and investigated "how dominant ideologies of English are naturalized into knowledge and commonsensical meanings" (Xiong and Qian, 2012, p. 76). The analysis of the

textbook *Advance with English Student's Book 3* (published in 2004), a Chinese senior high school textbook, discussed three issues: (1) "a selective representation of the history of English", (2) "shallow sociolinguistic explanations", and (3) "grammatical prescriptivism" (Xiong and Qian, 2012, p. 76). They discussed ideologies of English in China before their main analysis, and then built a research framework to investigate ideological aspects with a CDA approach (Xiong and Qian, 2012).

This thesis aims to provide a more comprehensive, holistic and relatively detailed and multidimensional analysis of sociocultural and ideological aspects of the contents of conversations of *Vision 3* textbook which is the 12th grade schoolbook for senior high school, through critical discourse analysis based on Fairclough's three dimensional model. The textbook's recent publication and the narrower focus of preceding critical discourse analysis studies in the past on specific aspects such as gender representation or gender bias, make this study different from preceding CDA studies on textbooks.

Chapter Three

Methodology

The method of this study was qualitative research based on critical discourse analysis.

3.1 Model

This study has used Norman Fairclough's three-dimensional model as a framework for conducting an investigation of ideological and sociocultural elements of conversation parts of Vision 3 textbook. As a study with critical discourse analysis approach, this study examines the textual, as well as sociolinguistic aspects of the textbook conversations.

The three dimensions of exploring critical discourse analysis are:

1. Text and its characteristics
2. Discursive practice: Production and consumption of text
3. Social practice

Fairclough's three-dimensional model provides an empirical and methodological framework for critical discourse analysis. The three interrelated dimensions build the foundation and base for critical studies of language use aiming to find the aspects and elements of language use which create and affect the relationship between language use, social relations and power relations in a dialectical and bilateral dynamic relationship.

Fairclough's model has methodological flexibility and is a framework, not a master plan. In each study, modifications can be made in the components and subjects of the dimensions based on the specific research objectives, material and subject and the context.

Fairclough's three-dimensional model is a model for performing CDA, and CDA is an approach of qualitative inquiry. That argues for the possibility and necessity of a researcher's modification based on the exploratory needs and aims.

In Fairclough's model, the concepts, elements or components of high importance in any CDA study are communicative event, discursive order and

genre and characteristics of text. These three components are relevant to all three dimensions of the model to different extents.

In the present study, each of the six conversations of Vision 3 textbook was analyzed in terms of the three dimensions. Also, three "*sub-dimensions*" or "*subcomponents*" have been proposed for the dimension "Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text", which are: "*Communicative Event and the Discursive Order*", "*Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose*" and "*Situational Level: Context and Scenario*". Moreover, the two subcomponents "*Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References*" and "*Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias*" have been suggested and utilized to conduct the analysis of the dimension "Social Practice".

I proposed these sub-dimensions or subcomponents for each dimension of Fairclough's model as relevant aspects of each dimension. This was done to enable me to conduct the analysis.

In the first dimension (text), speaker's role in handling the dialogue, word choice, semantic and pragmatic issues, figurative and metaphorical expressions, style and linguistic elements of text have been analyzed.

In the second dimension, communicative event, situation, context and instructional purposes have been investigated.

In the third dimension, values, ideology and social relations have been explored.

Figure 3-1. Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional discourse analysis model. (Kaur, Arumugam & Yunus, 2013)

Figure 3-2. Discourse and speech as social act: Social dimensions of discourse (Ross & Rivers, 2017)

Figure 3-3. Text, discursive practice and social practice – Fairclough's model's three dimensions and their subcategories (Abdul Malek, et al, 2017)

Figure 3-4. Text, discursive and social practice (Xinling Tian, 2018)

Figure 3-5. Illustration of Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model (Matthiessen, 2012)

Figure 3-6. Components of Fairclough's 2001 three-dimensional model in details (Kabugo, Masaazi & Mugagga, 2015)

3.2 Procedure

In this thesis, the critical discourse analysis of the conversations of Vision 3 textbook was composed of two parts: First, each of the six conversations of the textbook has been analyzed in terms of the three dimensions of Fairclough's three-dimensional model and the proposed sub-dimensions which I have introduced. The second part of the analysis is holistic analysis of different characteristics, elements and aspects of the conversations.

In the holistic analysis, the six conversations have been examined as a whole and the themes, topics, values, ideas and speakers' characteristics have been discussed in relation to each other. The frequency and number of occurrence of some of the characteristics have been checked for use in extracting and identifying the underlying elements of ideology and culture.

3.3 Corpus

The corpus data of the study consist of the six conversations of Vision 3 textbook which are presented in the two sections: "Conversation" and "Listening and Speaking". The latest copy of the book has been used for analysis. Since its introduction in 2019, the textbook has not undergone any change or revision (Ministry of Education OERP, 2020, 2021).

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

4.1 Overview

The goal of this thesis was to conduct a critical discourse analysis of instructional conversations of Vision 3 textbook based on Fairclough's three-dimensional model which investigates the sociocultural and ideological aspects of discursive and social practice within the textbook conversations.

There are six conversations in Vision 3 textbook, as there are three lessons and each lesson has two conversations within the sections "Conversation" and "Listening and Speaking", each section having one conversation. If a conversation is defined as an instance of a communicative interaction between at least two people in form of speaking, the abovementioned sections would fall in the criteria of containing a conversation. At the beginning of the book and after the introduction, there is a three-page part titled "Map of Vision 3" which lists the sections of each lesson and the objectives, or topics and subjects of each section. The mentioned aims and proposed objectives in this part have been considered in analysis of conversations.

This analysis is mainly based on and founded upon Norman Fairclough's three-dimensional model of critical discourse analysis which considers language usage as social practice and investigates the sociopolitical, ideological and communicative aspects of discourse (language use and text) in three interrelated, overlapping and interwoven "layers", "dimensions" or "areas" which are "text, its production and its consumption", "discursive practice" and "social practice" (Fairclough, 1992b, 1993, 1995a&b, 2010; Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 1999; Yarmohammadi, 2014). Due to the fact that Fairclough's model is methodologically flexible and provides a "general pattern" and an analytical, empirical and methodological framework for critical analysis of discourse and not a "blueprint", three "*sub-dimensions*" or "*subcomponents*" have been proposed for the dimension "Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text", which are: "*Communicative Event and the Discursive Order*", "*Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose*" and "*Situational Level: Context and Scenario*". Moreover,

the two subcomponents "*Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References*" and "*Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias*" have been suggested and utilized to conduct the analysis of the dimension "Social Practice".

It is worth mentioning that due to the nature of textbooks' instructive conversations as imaginary written dialogues with pedagogical and instructional goals, topic selection, content development and choices of linguistic items such as word selection should also be analyzed for assessment of educational efficiency of the sample conversations. I have attempted to partially cover these areas in the first layer or dimension known as *text* and the second one, *discursive practice*.

The conversations of Vision 3 textbook are on pages 19, 32, 47, 61, 75 and 89.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Conversation One

4.2.1.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.1.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

Before the conversation text, a description of the situation and imaginary scenario of the conversation has been given. The sample conversation is between an adolescent patient named "Sara" and a nurse in *Children's Medical Center*. Sara begins the conversation by asking a question following the politeness expression "Excuse me". This term of politeness is for the purpose of beckoning and initiating the conversation. Throughout the conversation, the whole speech of the nurse is for the purpose of answering the patient's questions and responding to her enquiries and curiosity, as Sara asks for information and the nurse replies. The nurse obviously talks more and has the larger share of sentences in the conversation. While the adolescent patient begins the conversation and practically determines the topic, the nurse is the speaker with more knowledge and information and performs the role of "a guide" for the patient, similar to the role of a guide in relation to a visitor in a museum. The nurse, in the first sentence she utters in the conversation, responds to Sara's question by asking two questions. The second question has informative nature and is adequate to be considered a proper answer, while the first is apparently expression of surprise about the fact

that the patient does not know the old man whose picture is on the wall. ("Oh, don't you know him?")

The real-life event or fact of inclusion of Dr. Gharib's name and biographic information in the English textbook has been portrayed in the conversation with the narrative method *story-in-story* as Sara vaguely and doubtfully recalls seeing his name in her "*English book*" in the second adjacency pair or the fourth line. Having an English book mentioning the name of an Iranian famous person indicates that the textbook is used at the school and one can use background knowledge of Iranian schools to infer that the girl is in adolescence. Hence, this part can be considered as clue to Sara's age.

Perhaps it would have been better in terms of narrativity and it would have been narratively more convincing and appealing if the authors had instead referred to the TV series about Dr. Gharib's life. In other words, they could have written this part of the scenario in a way that Sara vaguely and doubtfully remembered a TV series once on air on a national television channel, instead of the textbook. In the textbook, the TV series instead has been mentioned in the section titled "Questions" which comes after the conversation. I believe the opposite practice would be more credible.

After the nurse tells Sara who Dr. Gharib was and informs her of his occupation, Sara shows interest and seems impressed as she asks "Oh,... can you tell me a little about his life?" The short pause after the interjection or exclamation "Oh" suggests enthusiasm.

I suggest that using "a little bit" instead of "a little" could teach the learners one more vocabulary item and would be therefore more enriching regarding vocabulary development.

Patient's expression of interest happens in the seventh line of the conversation and the third adjacency pair. The nurse answers by uttering five sentences, making this part of the conversation the longest part. This is also the longest turn of a speaker and the longest part in any adjacency pair among all the conversations of the whole textbook. The response by the nurse consists of five lines. The remarks and statements she gives begin with telling Sara about Dr. Gharib's birthplace and the year he was born. The nurse takes her turn and replies

to the query by saying five formal sentences similar to narration of a documentary. A rather odd and uncommon characteristic of her utterances is saying the year (1288 A. H.) and beginning by a number memorized by her. It seems kind of unusual for a real conversation and an instance of day-to-day speaking; moreover, it seems unusual for a nurse to keep the hospital founder's year of birth in her memory. A more natural and credible approach would be using the phrase "about one hundred years ago" instead.

The nurse then continues with briefly providing general information about Dr. Gharib's education, his studies abroad and the year of his graduation and his return to Iran. ("In 1316 he became a physician and then came back to his homeland.")

Again, it is observed that remembering Dr. Gharib's year of graduation is a bit unusual. Perhaps using the phrase "his homeland" here has been done purposefully to create a sense of patriotism. After this, the final sentence the nurse utters at the end of her turn in this adjacency pair is mentioning the year the hospital was established. Once again, a year with its chronological or calendar number is mentioned.

In the turn of the nurse in this adjacency pair and out of the five sentences she utters, there are two sentences with passive voice: the first sentence and the last one. The first sentence which opens and begins the turn is "Dr. Gharib was born in Tehran in 1288." The combination "be born" is used by native speakers exactly like this, thus its inclusion is of authentic linguistic value. The last sentence, however, is different. In the last sentence, the use of passive voice for the intended meaning of the sentence is unnecessary and probably rather unlikely to happen if a native speaker wants to convey and express the same meaning, as passive voice is less frequently used than active voice in an average native speaker's day-to-day speaking, except for the situations when the focus is on the object. In general, active voice is preferred over passive voice and is more frequently used, unless really necessary (Beare, 2019; Orwell, 1946; Zwicky, 2006; Fowler, 2009 & 2015; Wilson, 1992; Bowkett, 2020; Lee & Doherty, 2018). Passive voice is more often used when it is not important to mention the person who does something (Lee & Doherty, 2018). That is in contrast to the

conversation's situation, as the nurse is telling the patient about the life of Dr. Gharib who founded the hospital, and the hospital itself is not of the main importance or primary focus. Also, another piece of supporting evidence for discouraging the use of passive voice is that the automated grammatical checker subsystem of Microsoft Office Word software often suggests revision when passive voice is used in a sentence (Wyatt, 2019).

It can be inferred that authors have used passive voice excessively because it is the topic of the grammar section of the lesson and they have done this so that the conversation section helps in learning the grammatical structure taught in the grammar section of the lesson. This practice is in fact sacrificing the authenticity of the conversation and its natural form in favor of teaching grammar. The communicative aspect of the conversation is even more weakened by this strategy, as real expression of intended meaning within the designed situation would be less likely accomplished by passive voice grammatical structure.

This approach is rather unnecessary as there are enough examples and materials in the grammar section to reinforce and foster learning.

The fourth adjacency pair begins with Sara's expression of surprise and being impressed, uttering the non-interrogative question "Really?!" preceding the sentence "I didn't know that" expressing lack of prior information or knowledge. The nurse replies by even more admiration for Dr. Gharib and providing more information on his service and dedication.

This time, again, the nurse takes a long turn, uttering four sentences. She tells the adolescent patient about Dr. Gharib's virtues, good morals and philanthropic character. It begins by attributing the adjective "generous" to him, followed by the adjectives "friendly" and "helpful" and she also informs Sara of charitable activities of Dr. Gharib and his humanitarian deeds. ("... helpful to poor families.")

The metaphorical (figurative) verb phrase "spared no pains" has been used to show Dr. Gharib's dedication, commitment and passion emphatically. ("He spared no pains to cure sick children."). This idiomatic expression is also presented in the textbox "*Word Bank*" on the top of the conversation as a new expression the students should learn (See p. 19).

The discourse marker and adverb phrase "Not surprisingly" has been used with function of intensification and emphasis. This expression is also listed in the *Word Bank* subsection.

For the purpose of showing the public's respect for Dr. Gharib or portraying others' view on his personality, the verb "*regard*" has been used. "... he was regarded as a dedicated physician."

People's opinion about Dr. Gharib and being "regarded" as a *dedicated physician* have been described to be due to his virtues and positive characteristics mentioned earlier. ("Not surprisingly, he was ...")

A new adjacency pair begins by Sara saying "It's a pity! I didn't know such a great man."

This reveals Sara's regret that she had not known Dr. Gharib earlier. She considers not knowing him before "*a pity*". A more suitable form to use instead of these two separate sentences could be their combination as one sentence:

"It's a pity [~~that~~] I didn't know such a great man."

The nurse continues by telling the adolescent patient about Dr. Gharib's academic achievements as a "*distinguished university professor*, author of "*the first Persian textbook on children's diseases*" and being the instructor of thousands of medical students.

In the three sentences the nurse utters in this turn, two sentences contain passive voice as the fundamental grammatical structure they have been developed upon. These two sentences are "He was known as a distinguished university professor, too." and "The first Persian textbook on children's diseases was written by him." Even if one considers the use of passive voice in the first sentence as acceptable, its usage in the latter (the one before the last in this turn) is unnecessary, as it can simply be "He wrote the first Persian textbook on children's diseases."

It seems that the authors have chosen to use passive voice more often to provide linguistic input aiming to reinforce and strengthen student's learning of passive voice grammatical structure. This has been done with negligence and degradation of communicative authenticity and naturalness of the conversation—

that is, presentation of real spoken language as native speakers are more likely to speak without clumsiness, artificiality and wordiness.

The nurse invokes even more admiration to the already astonished patient who in return says, "Oh, what a great man he was!" and begins a new adjacency pair by expressing her amazement and wonder through this sentence.

In this utterance of Sara and in what she said in the opening of the former adjacency pair ("It's a pity! ... great man."), repetitive and redundant use of the word "great" in two sentences can be observed, as another synonymous word or a lexical item of similar meaning in either sentences could improve the style and elegance of this part of the text, as well as teaching the learners a new word or expression. This matters both in terms of vocabulary building and beauty of style, thus I suggest it would be better to use another word, such as excellent, honorable, awesome, amazing, marvelous, remarkable, brilliant, etc., all used in corpuses of natural linguistic production by native speakers for describing people they admire (Ludwig SRLS *ludwig.guru*, 2022).

After Sara opens the sixth and last adjacency pair by saying "Oh, what a great man he was!" in response to the remarks of the nurse in the second turn of the preceding adjacency pair, the nurse uses the discourse marker "By the way ..." to introduce and propose a new topic or to give information about a fact. She begins with saying "... it might be interesting to know that ...", so that she can prepare the listener for what she is about to say, elicit enthusiasm, bring about desire for knowing and invoke curiosity in the listener. Familiarizing the students with this situational communicative strategy and illustrating how it can be used along with the widely-used idiomatic expression "by the way" are positive points and can be considered merits of this instructive conversation. The phrase "by the way" which signals introduction of a new topic or indicates subject change, is used in real life conversations and therefore, is of instructive and communicative value.

Following the use of two discourse markers and introducing expressions to open her turn, the nurse informs the patient that her physician was once a student of Dr. Gharib. The information and statement in the nurse's utterance cause Sara to express surprise once again. She utters "Really?! That's interesting!"

Earlier in the conversation, in the thirteenth line (p. 19) and in Sara's turn in the fourth adjacency pair (first turn in that pair), Sara has used the same word to express surprise and wonder. ("Really?!") The repetition of the same word for the same purpose (expressing surprise or being impressed), is questionable both in terms of style and regarding limitation of instructive input. Hearing and reading the same word again would arguably cause the listener or reader to become bored and lose interest. Introducing another way to show surprise or interest in a conversation would also be of high pedagogic, linguistic and communicative value.

One way for a native speaker of English from British, American, Australian or Canadian culture (as some of English-speaking cultures) to show surprise and interest in response to a speaker's utterance is using the interjection or exclamation "Wow!" which can be heard from many native speakers in many different situations, even semi-formal contexts. It can be inferred that among the reasons the authors have avoided the inclusion of this word, are their tendency to formalism and teaching formal language, their possible hesitation, reluctance and disinterest to present the original "foreign" culture and their possible belief that such colloquial, informal and spoken terms are of low instructive value.

Textbooks and especially, language textbooks are expected to present accurate, correct and mistake-free texts which are grammatically and linguistically precise. Due to the role and function of textbooks, they are supposed to contain texts that are accurate in terms of spelling, grammar, punctuation and wording. The use of correct punctuation marks is important in any text and more important in instructional materials intended for learners. A textbook like Vision 3 which is used nationwide is even more required to meet these criteria.

The semantic and pragmatic role of the utterance "Really" on page 19, in the thirteenth line of main text of conversation (in black typeset) and in Sara's opening (first) turn, and on page 20, in the twelfth line, (again in Sara's turn, as final closing utterance), is exactly the same, as in both places it conveys the meaning that the speaker is surprised or impressed, but one can see that on page 19, there is only a question mark after it, and no exclamation mark, despite the fact that it has the semantic, conceptual and pragmatic property of transferring a

message of surprise, amazement or wonder, on the other hand, on page 20, the same linguistic sequence or utterance with the same semantic and pragmatic role (the same meaning), has been used with an exclamation mark. This double standard is a mistake that can affect learners' understanding, however slightly and subtly, either consciously or unconsciously.

The conversation is ended by Sara's utterance which acts similar to the topic bounding technique in a three-part interchange that closes the conversation and ends the dialogue exchange. The repeated routine, trend or norm in this conversation is the beginning of adjacency pairs by Sara, with either a query (in the first half of the conversation) or expression of amazement and admiration (mainly in the second half of the conversation) and the response from the nurse in the second turn which contains information about Dr. Gharib's virtues and achievements, ending the pair. In the final pair, however, after the turn by the nurse, Sara shows approval and interest like her previous turns, but also signals the closure and end of the conversation by signaling agreement with the nurse's claim that the presented fact might be interesting, and the conversation is complete.

Due to the possible opportunity of teaching a new word being missed by repetitive use of the adjective "interesting", I suggest it would be better if another adjective with a similar meaning were used so that a new lexical item could be taught. Examples can be fascinating, amazing, wonderful or even a combination like "That's great / nice to know!"

The conversation is both begun and ended by Sara who either asks questions and shows interest and curiosity or expresses her surprise about Dr. Gharib's achievements and her admiration for him.

The conversation consists of six adjacency pairs and thirteen turns. Sara has seven turns and the nurse has six turns, but the length of the utterances of the nurse is more and she has the bigger share of speaking.

It is worth mentioning that the clue to the gender of the nurse is the audio piece of the conversation in the compact disc that contains the audio files of textbook. In the audio file, the nurse has a feminine voice.

4.2.1.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

Discursive practice in critical discourse analysis deals with the aspects and characteristics of language use within the communicative context. Two elements, layers or properties in this dimension of Fairclough's three-dimensional model are the *communicative event* (the occurrence, situation and the pragmatic goal which connect the parties involved and affect their interaction) and the discursive order (the genre and rules of language use which are relevant to the context and pragmatic purpose) (Yarmohammadi, 2014a,b&c)

As this conversation is an instructive and instructional sample text within a textbook, I have also added the subcomponent *instructive level*, which deals with the pedagogic, educational, linguistic and communicative aims and objectives the authors of this textbook have had in mind, have planned and have attempted to fulfill and cater for.

4.2.1.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

Based on the description before the conversation and the utterances exchanged within it, the conversation occurs when a juvenile patient at hospital, a girl named Sara, sees the picture of an "old man" (picture of late Dr. Mohammad Gharib, Iranian pioneer in pediatrics) on the wall which invokes her curiosity. When the nurse "takes her temperature", Sara addresses the nurse and asks her about the man whose picture is on the wall. The nurse replies and introduces him to Sara. This provokes her curiosity even more and makes her want to know more and increases her willingness to know. She quests more information and shows interest and the nurse goes on, providing the patient more information on Dr. Gharib's identity, traits and achievements. Sara expresses her interest in the topic three times in the conversation and in one final closing utterance. Except for this final utterance, each time she shows being attracted by the topic and being curious to know more about it, the nurse provides her more biographic information about Dr. Gharib.

The nature of conversation between Sara and the nurse is that of an adolescent seeking information from an adult by asking a question. Another basic and intrinsic characteristic of their conversational interaction which is of

fundamental importance, is the institutional essence of the conversation, as this happens in an institution or organization (a hospital) and the client-agent (patient-nurse) relationship which is made as the first speaker (Sara who starts the conversation and asks a question and is a person who has come to receive service) expects the other person (the nurse who provides the service to Sara as her nurse) to know the answer to her question. The nurse has come to take Sara's temperature as a technical routine within the medical procedures executed as part of her treatment, but Sara seizes the opportunity to ask her a question about what she (= Sara) sees in the surrounding environment and expects the nurse to know the answer, as the place is her workplace and she is an employee or a staff member there. The hospital is a context which is an example of a social environment and social institution where human interaction occurs and needs are satisfied (Sara has caught a "terrible flu" and stays there to "get better"). This institution is relevant to "a great man" who has founded the institution and another person who provides service to the patient (her physician) has been once a student of the founder of the hospital. Through all these, there is a portrayal and representation of legacy, influence and impact of Dr. Gharib, a "famous physician" and "a distinguished university professor" whose great qualities, activities and achievements fascinates the young patient.

A picture of the founder of the hospital where Sara is hospitalized on the wall of the hospital room invokes her curiosity and she is amazed and astonished by nice qualities and achievements of the founder when the nurse tells her about them.

The language used by the two parties involved in the conversation is formal. A characteristic of Sara's utterances is politeness ("Excuse me..."). The nurse uses friendly style in answering and providing information, but is not casual or informal. This is a characteristic of language used in institutional interaction, similar to business interaction in a workplace. There are no terms of endearment and affection, though there could be. The nurse intends to keep her relationship with the patient a formal one. The patient, too, begins by formal language and keeps the formal language even in expression of enthusiasm, approval and willingness for knowing more.

It can be inferred that the authors have intended to introduce a famous and honorable character, show how he could deeply influence others' lives, how he served his society and how he left a legacy of great achievements. This is discussed in more details in the section about the next dimension.

The communicative event is a casual and perhaps on-the-spot (unplanned) conversation of *question-and-answer* type which has happened in the margin of a non-verbal (non-linguistic) professional service-providing act (taking the patient's temperature) in which a client (patient in a hospital) asks a member of the staff (a nurse) for information about the surrounding environment (place) and the purpose for asking the question is indulging and satisfying her curiosity. The presence of an old man's photo on the wall of the room in a hospital stimulates the patient's curiosity and it is obvious she is sociable enough to start a conversation and ask. The identity of the person whose photo is on the wall of the hospital room is unknown to the patient and the act of decorating the wall with the photo makes Sara ask a question. She then becomes interested in having more detailed information on the life of the man (a famous physician).

People engaged and involved in this conversation are of the same gender (both female) and one (the patient) is there to receive service (healthcare) and the other (nurse) is there as a service provider who does an occupational activity as part of her job. She answers the girl's questions attentively and with some passion or interest, giving her relatively detailed information on the topic she has asked about. It may be reasonable enough to mention that the act of taking a patient's temperature logically takes less time than the time necessary for the conversation, so one might infer that the nurse kindly and nicely answers the questions of a young patient about the founder of the hospital. The nurse is not in a hurry and has substantial respect for the person whose life is the topic of the conversation. She does not quit soon, simply uttering two minimal sentences like "He was the founder of this hospital and a professor of medicine" and goes into details which she thinks might be interesting to the patient.

The utterances exchanged between the two persons involved in the conversation are in formal language. There is expression of feelings or emotions on the side of Sara, but she and the nurse both use formal language. The way the

nurse talks about Dr. Gharib's life resembles formal narration of a documentary or reading a text, especially because of three times of mentioning numbers (years).

The topic of the conversation, proposed by the first speaker (the patient) is not a necessary part of what she is there for and what the nurse has come to do, it is rather a kind of casual conversation started by a possibly bored patient (she has been there for a week now, as said in the description on the top of the conversation text), who is curious and also interested in knowing more about "a great man".

4.2.1.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

On the first page of "Map of Vision 3" part which functions as the table of contents and list of sections, titles and objectives of lessons, the description of lesson's conversation section declares its objective as "Talking about a Great Person". The title of the lesson is "Sense of Appreciation".

The topic of the conversation section of the lesson suggests that, it has been among authors' intended goals to introduce an honorable and well-respected figure and provide the learners with some words, phrases, expressions and patterns for talking about the life of a famous and respectable person. Here, the honorable and "great" person is a physician and university professor. Some adjectives for description of positive qualities and socially-desirable characteristics (virtues) have been also provided.

The aim of the conversation section is not to prepare and equip the students for a real communicative task for which knowledge and skills of a foreign language (here, English) are necessary, or at least, the aim is not to prepare students for a real world communicative task that they prioritize or one which serves their educational, academic, occupational or general needs, nor does it represent or resemble an objective of foreign language learning the students are familiar with or can imagine, e. g. getting information in a situation where a foreign language is necessary, like a conversation between a tourist and a local.

Presence of cultural and ideological goals in choosing the topic and the objective is evident by understanding the fact that service, achievements and philanthropy of a famous Iranian physician is discussed in the conversation. A

physician who has studied abroad, but "returned to his homeland", "spared no pains to cure sick children" and "was friendly and helpful to poor families".

Languages are means of communication and mutual understanding. Language learning is a major goal followed by learners for gaining linguistic skills, competencies and abilities which benefit their lives' different aspects. In all life aspects that might be intended to benefit from language learning, there is always a type of "communication" that is necessary. Examples are travelling, studying, business and trade, etc. Therefore, planning and designing learning materials such as textbooks should be done with attention to language-related real life needs. I believe, the presented conversation hardly serves any real life need and if it does, it is done poorly. People around the world use foreign languages as *lingua franca* and *second language* and this is not something that happens in this conversation, as the both participating parties are Iranian and it is happening in Iran. A conversation is a sample of speaking and oral language use and not a text that is going to transfer a few words, expressions and patterns. Conversations in textbooks are the only speaking-related resource of input some learners may have access to, and should be systematically relevant to real life speaking. A conversation is not only a section in a textbook to teach words, phrases or common sentences, it should be based on realistic context and some communicative task to be effective, otherwise, a reading passage would even do the job better. It is important to teach the way words and expressions are used in spoken language, but this requires natural and authentic input that relates to communicative tasks and needs, is similar to native speakers' linguistic production and improves the ability to communicate in the taught language. I believe this conversation does not meet these criteria.

It is fair and rational to expect a conversation in a textbook to teach the learners how they can have a conversation in real life, but asking about the life of a great person whose picture is on the wall of the hospital's room after a week of hospitalization is not something that often occurs!

4.2.1.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

The summary of the scenario of the conversation and the situations it occurs in is that, an Iranian adolescent girl, named Sara, catches "a terrible flu" and is hospitalized. She has to stay in the hospital for more than a week. She notices an old man's "*photograph*" on the wall of the room. (Note the use of the old-fashioned, archaic and obsolete (Stack Exchange, 2015) formal word "photograph" which is rarely used in everyday English (*Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 2019) in the description given before the conversation on page 19 of the textbook) One day, a nurse comes to "take her temperature". Sara asks her who the old man in the picture is. She replies and tells her the name of the man (who is late Dr. Mohammad Gharib) and that he was a "famous physician". Sara becomes more interested and asks the nurse to tell her "a little about his life". She tells Sara about the works, services, virtues and legacy of Dr. Gharib. Sara regrets not knowing about him earlier and becomes fascinated to his life. The nurse finally tells her that the physician curing her is a former student of late Dr. Gharib.

This is the scenario and story of the context of a conversation in an English language textbook designed for high school students of the twelfth grade (last grade before receiving high school diploma). In the conversation's situation, two Iranians are talking about a deceased Iranian who was an honorable and well-respected physician, among the first and the best in his profession during his lifetime.

The situation can be considered unrealistic as it is not a context in which one can expect use of English language. The situation is very specific and special and can hardly be generalized and simulated to be used as a sample to make a new conversation. It is not a good sample and pattern for most conversations a language learner really needs.

The only action taken to make the conversation seem natural and believable is the use of the interjection "oh" in the beginning of three sentences. One uttered by the nurse in expression of surprise about, or interest in Sara's initial question ("Oh, don't you know him?") and the two other times uttered by

Sara as parts of her reactions to hearing about the virtues and achievements of Dr. Gharib.

Sara says she can vaguely and doubtfully remember Dr. Gharib's name in her English book, but is not sure. The reality that the authors of the textbook have included the topic of Dr. Gharib's life in it is reflected in the story of the conversation, perhaps to make it lively and vivid or more credible, though this has not added to the communicative value of the conversation, nor has this led to teaching new words or expressions.

In the situation and scenario of the conversation, Sara enthusiastically listens to, and asks about, some facts about Dr. Gharib's life. This can bring to the mind the idea that she has received good healthcare service that feels well enough to notice her surroundings and attentively listen to what the nurse says about Dr. Gharib's life. Note that, according to the description above the conversation text, she has caught "a terrible flu" and that the doctor has "told her to stay there to get better".

This conversation is the first of the three conversations of this textbook in which a person's working place is where the conversation occurs.

4.2.1.1.3 Social Practice

Human beings live in societies which contain groups and institutions. People in societies have diverse relationships with other people and these relationships are of different types, functions, roles and complexity levels. Each person within a society is a member of several groups and has multiple relationships with different people inside and outside the groups she/he is a member (Bell & Newby, 2021; Blau, 2017). In these relationships, communication is vitally important and essential for the proper interaction that is necessary for the relationship to function and serve the intended purposes. Verbal communication through language use and performing speech acts is critically indispensable and integral in fulfillment of aims and satisfying needs within social relations (Hidayat, 2016). A goal of education and educational systems should be preparation of people for living in the society, facilitating their integration in the society, teaching socially acceptable behaviors and transferring social values

(Idris, et al, 2012). These goals should be followed with respect for individuality, personal freedom and creativity of people and should not interfere with their unique personal identity. (Côté, 2005; Kim & Marcus, 1999; Jansen & Van Der Veen, 1997; Goodman, 1989; Cagan, 1978).

The first conversation of the first lesson of Vision 3 textbook contains and presents social aspects and sociocultural elements that are discussed in the next two subsections.

4.2.1.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

There are historical and ideological references in the content of the conversation.

Dr. Mohammad Gharib is an Iranian scientific and historical figure. Mentioning his departure abroad for studying medicine, can be considered a historical reference to the practice of sending students abroad for obtaining and gaining education and receiving professional training. The tradition of sending talented students or students of upper-class families abroad began in the middle of Qajar dynasty period and continued since then. Dr. Mohammad Gharib was among the first group of students on foreign expedition to France for medical education. He went abroad during the early years of first period of Pahlavi dynasty.

Reference to establishing the first pediatric hospital in Iran is another historical reference.

Concerning the ideological references, the qualities and characteristics proposed as necessary for considering a physician as "a dedicated physician" are worthy of attention. Dr. Gharib, a pioneer in his specialty, "was regarded as a dedicated physician" because he "was a generous man" and "spared no pains to cure sick children"; and because he "was very friendly and helpful to poor families".

4.2.1.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

In addition to the moral and ethical values proposed in the content of the conversation text as virtues and positive qualities (generosity, friendliness, helpfulness, philanthropy towards the poor), admiration of Dr. Gharib's scientific works and achievements and his contribution to the society and "*his homeland*" are relevant to the intended and desired values of the Iranian education system and the textbook authors.

Dr. Mohammad Gharib is paid tribute in the conversation content and has been referred to as a "great man" two times. Also, the section objective is "talking about a great person" and Dr. Gharib is an example of a great person introduced in the conversation text. The characteristics proposed as the qualities of a great man are presented with description of Dr. Gharib's life, characteristics, contribution and influence.

Within the conversation scenario, it is observed that an adolescent patient receives critical healthcare service in a hospital founded by Dr. Gharib and the physician who provides the treatment has been once one of Dr. Gharib's students. This is, I believe, illustration and representation of the concept of cooperation between generations in the society. This is also a reference to the concept of legacy and the contribution and influence of a person continuously serving the members of the society after his/her death. Celebration and commemoration of those serving the society is another theme in the conversation related to some social value.

It is observed that the adolescent patient is uninformed about the topic of the conversation and the nurse is the informing participant in the conversation who acts as the source of information to the young patient. While it is generally considered normal and acceptable for a person of lower age to have less knowledge, the difference in having information between the two conversation parties is obvious.

A brief value-driven and ideological reference to the notion of acceptable and desirable behavior towards impoverished people is presented in the sentence "He was very friendly and helpful to poor families" and the word "generous"

4.2.1.2 Critical Observations and Notes

The sample conversation is not an example of real spoken language. Everyday conversations in real life are different from the dialogue in this conversation text. Day-to-day conversations by native speakers usually contain shorter sentences, more informal language and use of some colloquial terms.

Authenticity and communicative value of the conversation text is relatively low, as it does not have much use in communicative tasks and functions of real life situations. It is also different from native speakers' language use and deviates from usual style of conversations in which English is used a lingua franca. Moreover, a typical conversation between two non-native speakers using International English as a communicative tool is also different from bookish and book-like sentences the nurse in the conversation scenario utters.

Absence of real and authentic communicative functions in the conversation is another considerable issue.

Examples of real and authentic communicative functions are introducing two persons or oneself, greeting, thanking somebody or simply something in real life done naturally through natural use of English language. After all, in how many, and what percentage of real life situations are we going to talk about a great person? Conversations in textbooks should serve the purpose of teaching speaking skill and should be patterns and resources of authentic input for development of speaking skill. This is another problem observed in this conversation.

What happens in this conversation's scenario is that two Iranians are talking about Dr. Gharib's life (a famous Iranian person), but use English to talk about him. They speak English in a situation irrelevant to any plausible and credible situation where using English language is reasonable. This makes the conversation seem unnatural and unauthentic. The intended audiences of the textbook who are high school students are also unlikely to relate themselves to the situation in which the conversation occurs.

The style of the dialogues exchanged, especially on the side of the nurse, is more like a reading passage. Mentioning the years with numbers and long sentences make the text more suitable for a reading comprehension passage rather than a conversation.

4.2.2 Conversation Two

4.2.2.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.2.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

The sample conversation consists of three adjacency pairs and six turns. The conversation is between two people and its text has six lines, each turn coming in one line of the text.

There is no mention of the names of the two speakers and no reference to their names and gender is given, making it impossible to infer anything about these characteristics of theirs.

This conversation is the second conversation in Vision 3 textbook and is the second conversation of the first lesson. It is featured in "Listening and Speaking" section on page 32. Based on the information on page 10 in the part "Map of Vision 3", the aim and objective of the sample conversation is "Eliciting Agreements and Signaling Uncertainty" which has been also provided on the top of the conversation in a textbox titled "Speaking Strategy". The main instructional and educational goal of this section and its sample conversation is teaching the students how they can use "tag questions" for the abovementioned objective.

The activity direction A (the guidelines) on page 32 declares the reasons of using "tag questions" (the main instructive aim of the section)

"We use 'tag questions' for two reasons: eliciting agreement (confirming facts) and signaling uncertainty."

Another "*reason*" of using tag question structure is making small talk and initiating conversations, as in "*Beautiful day, isn't it?*" (Saslow & Ascher, 2006). It is obvious that this usage which is of high communicative value has been missed and ignored, though it could have been presented for the benefit of the learners.

Based on the information on the textbox on the top of the page, the description of usage in part A and the table of contents of lesson one on page 10, the main goal of this section and its components is teaching the students the tag question structure with the presented usages ("eliciting agreement" and "signaling uncertainty"). These usages have been described as "Speaking Strategy" (See p. 32).

In this conversation, two colleagues are talking about another colleague of theirs who is now absent and has not come to work. They talk about his health and wellness. The name of the person whose health is the topic of the conversation is Sam.

The name "Sam" is uncommon and rare in Iran (the native country of the authors and the learners) if used at all, and its use may be considered as an attempt to simulate an imaginary situation in which native speakers of English language are speaking.

The first speaker (neither of the two speakers' names has been mentioned) initiates the conversation by two statements. The second statement is followed by a tag question:

"Sam has not come to work. I've heard he's sick, isn't he?"

Unlike the second sentence (or statement) in this turn of the first speaker where the modal *have* has been used in contracted form ("I've"), the negative form of this modal for third person singular in the first sentence is in full form ("has not" instead of "hasn't"). As this conversation has been intended to be a sample of spoken language in which short forms of modals and auxiliary verbs are used, and as a conformed and harmonious action in using the same modal, it would be better if the short (contracted) form of the modal *have* (here, "*hasn't*") had been used in the first sentence of the first speaker.

The second speaker replies by confirming what the first speaker has heard and says:

"Oh, yes. He was not well yesterday."

The second speaker utters the interjection (exclamation) "oh" at the beginning of what she/he says in their response to the first speaker's statements and question. This can be considered both an interjection and discourse marker. Its use at the start of a verbal reaction to what the first speaker has said might convey the meaning of importance of the topic to the second speaker or that he/she is willing to talk about the proposed topic.

The answer given to the first speaker's tag question (her/his request for confirmation or "signaling uncertainty") includes positive or affirmative answer by using the word "yes" and referring to what has happened recently in near past

(yesterday). The information the first speaker has received is confirmed with an event mentioned by the second speaker who affirms the first speaker what she/he has heard is true and real, as it is relevant to what she/he has witnessed to happen "yesterday".

Using "*wasn't*" instead of "was not" could be better in terms of similarity to spoken language and following the same rules for all the sentences in the conversation.

It seems the people in this "workplace" are on first name basis, as they refer to their absent colleague by his first name "Sam".

After the first speaker receives confirmation about what she/he has heard and the reason Sam has not come to work, she/he asks for details, wanting to know more:

"What's wrong with him?"

It is apparent that the first speaker is willing to know Sam's health problem with more details.

The second speaker's answer (in the fourth turn in the conversation, the second turn of the second adjacency pair) is not very clear and straightforward. It involves some uncertainty and shortage of data:

"The doctors are checking his health condition."

This sentence indicates that there is not enough data available yet to determine for sure what the problem is and due to lack of sufficient information, the speaker does not know what the problem is, as the medical checks and examinations are in progress.

It is interesting that in this conversation scenario, "*doctors*" are checking the health status of Sam, not "his doctor", "the doctor" or "a doctor". Having more than one doctor to check his health condition indicates that Sam is relatively wealthy or considered an important person for his employer, because he can have more than one doctor check his condition.

The second speaker's avoidance of a clear-cut answer and his subtle refusal to express a certain answer could be observed. This matches the instructive aim of teaching the use of tag question for signaling uncertainty, as the sentence is in fact

a logical basis for the next sentence uttered by the first speaker as she/he begins a new adjacency pair:

"It isn't something serious, is it?"

The first speaker (the one who begins the conversation) appears to be worried and concerned about Sam's health and seeks comfort and consolation through obtaining the second speaker's agreement. The first speaker is uncertain about what she/he asks and is therefore worried and anxious and tries to elicit agreement to be soothed and reassured.

The second speaker does not utter a certain answer and avoids an absolute statement in response, but expresses agreement about what they both want about their colleague's health:

"I hope not."

This is the end of the conversation in the second turn of the third adjacency pair. In this sample, the first speaker starts the conversation and the second speaker finishes the dialogue.

As mentioned earlier, the names and gender of the speakers are unknown. The two conversation parties do not have a name in the conversation text. The utterances of the first speaker who begins the conversation are marked with a green bullet and the second speaker's utterances are marked with a red bullet. All the utterances of the second speaker are for answering the first speaker's questions and the second speaker does not propose a new topic or idea in the conversation.

The conversation could have continued for providing more input. A possible example could be:

- You're busy today; you can't come with me to visit him, can you?

- ...

I also suggest introducing and presenting the other usage of tag questions which has not been introduced. That usage is generating small talk and initiating a conversation. The sample conversation could be like:

- Beautiful day, isn't it?

- It really is. ...

- ...

Both of these two suggestions would be possible with shrinking and downsizing the large picture in the middle of the page and moving it a few centimeters upwards.

The fact that nothing is known about names and gender of the speakers in this conversation makes it unnatural and uncommon and different from a credible conversation similar to one in real life. This also unconsciously and inevitably makes the students unable to relate themselves to the conversation and its scenario, especially if it is used for role playing practice.

4.2.2.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

4.2.2.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

The communicative event is a conversation between two colleagues or friends who are talking about their mutual friend or colleague currently absent because of illness. The participants of the conversation exchange dialogues about their colleague's health.

4.2.2.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

The pedagogic purpose of the conversation is to familiarize the high school students with tag questions and the way this structure can be used in speaking for eliciting agreement and signaling one's uncertainty or checking the factuality of a statement for confirmation.

The aim of the section in which the conversation is presented, is to teach a structural pattern for speaking in specific situations and occasions where checking information or seeking agreement is necessary. This has been mentioned as a "Speaking Strategy" in the textbox above the conversation. The use of tag questions has been briefly explained in part A before the conversation.

4.2.2.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

In this conversation, two people who both know a third person (= Sam) are talking about him. One of them (the first speaker) has "heard he's sick" and the other is aware of his being unwell yesterday.

The context and situation in which the conversation takes place is a workplace such as a company or office. The clue to this inference is the first

speaker's utterance ("Sam has not *come* to *work*...") which implies the first speaker is *at work* herself/himself. Also, based on the first speaker's second sentence in her/his first turn (the one with the tag question, "I've heard ..."), there are people who know both Sam and the first speaker, as they have told him/her (= the first speaker) about Sam being sick. This suggests they are possibly members of the same group which can be an office or company where they work.

Sam is absent at work today and "was not well yesterday". It seems that the second speaker who knows Sam was unwell was in the same place with him then. This is another possible clue the people involved in the conversation are colleagues working in the same place.

This conversation is the second conversation among the three conversations in the textbook in which a person's workplace is mentioned and referred to. In this conversation, there is substantial probability the conversation is occurring in the workplace.

4.2.2.1.3 Social Practice

In addition to proposing use of tag questions for eliciting agreement and signaling uncertainty, there are a number of socio-communicative acts the conversation could relate with. These include expressing doubt about a worrying issue at times of uncertainty without being abrupt ("I hope not" instead of "I don't know" etc), using past events as evidence or proof in reasoning ("Sam has not come to work. I've heard he's sick, isn't he?", "Oh, yes. He was not well yesterday") which is an act of transferring (= communicating) the output of a speaker's cognitive processing to the listener, and talking about health condition of a mutual acquaintance.

4.2.2.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

There is no ideological or political reference in this conversation.

It might be interesting to some readers that this conversation is the only one in which a first name with usage among native speakers is used.

4.2.2.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

In this conversation, one of the speakers asks questions about the reason an acquaintance of her/him is absent at work, so that she/he can get some information about his health and wellbeing. Trying to find out whether an acquaintance, friend or colleague is seriously ill or not is a social behavior.

It seems that the second speaker does not want to give answers which can make the first speaker more worried, as she/he compensates her/his uncertainty and lack of information with some sentences that are somehow comforting to a worried person. By avoiding frank statement of cluelessness, the second speaker tries to soothe the first speaker's worries about Sam's health.

4.2.2.2 Critical Observations and Notes

Except for two sentences, the authors have used contracted forms in all other sentences whenever possible. As a conversation is a sample of spoken language and contracted forms are more frequently used than complete forms, especially in informal conversations like this one, it is suggested that it would be better if the authors had taken a homogeneous and equal action of using contracted forms whenever possible.

I believe reducing the size of the picture in the middle of the page could provide some space for continuing the conversation for the purpose of offering more input or proving another conversation with the same pedagogical and instructive goal or for the aim of introducing the use of tag questions for generating small talk and beginning a conversation.

4.2.3 Conversation Three

4.2.3.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.3.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

The third conversation of Vision 3 textbook is on page 27 and is between a teacher and a high school student. This conversation is the only one which occurs in an educational setting and is the only one in which the involved parties are a

teacher and a student. This conversation is in the section "Conversation" at the beginning of lesson two.

Lesson two's first conversation consists of nine adjacency pairs and a final turn. This conversation has two characters as the participants involved in it: Majid, the high school student and Mr. Iranmehr, the English teacher.

There is a description of the conversation's scenario and situation, before the conversation text and above it. The description consists of two sentences and two lines of text. It reads:

"Majid is going to choose a suitable dictionary for his English class. He is talking to his English teacher during the break."

The description reveals the place of the conversation and its context. The clue to this is the phrase "during the break" which suggests this is happening at school and most probably, in the classroom. The description also informs the reader of the topic of the conversation and its purpose. In the first sentence of the description, the intention of the first speaker, Majid, is reported: He "is going to choose a suitable dictionary for his English class". The structure "be+going to" has been used for expressing intention and will. In the second sentence of the description, what Majid "is doing" for actualizing and realizing his intention is reported using the present continuous tense. This gives the sense and impression of creating a snapshot of what is happening exactly right now and might be an attempt to make the conversation livelier and more vivid.

Majid is the first speaker and the one who starts the conversation. He uses the expression "Excuse me" before the surname of his teacher to politely address him for the purpose of beckoning, initiating the conversation and requesting. After addressing the teacher, he tells him his request: "I wonder if you could help me". The language style in Majid's first turn (also the first turn of the conversation) is formal and signals the use of formal language in the whole conversation. The wording in the sentence he utters complies with characteristics of formal language and signifies a polite formal request.

Like conversation one, this conversation is also started with the expression "Excuse me" in a similar way and for the same purpose: to get the attention of the intended listener and to begin the conversation in a polite and formal way.

Majid's utterance reveals he requests help, but does not disclose what he needs help with. This is what the teacher asks in the second turn of the conversation.

Mr. Iranmehr, Majid's English teacher, is the second speaker and responds to Majid's request by uttering "Sure. How can I help you?" and approves his student's request for help. He uses the word "Sure" to emphasize his willingness to help and asks Majid what he can do to help him.

In the third turn, Majid tells his teacher what help he needs. He tells the teacher he wants "some information" about "a good English dictionary". The contracted form of "would like" (I'd like) has been used for expressing what he wants.

Majid, a high school student, wants a dictionary to improve his English. He does not know much about dictionaries and asks his English teacher for guidance and information.

In the fourth turn of the conversation (the second turn of the second adjacency pair), the teacher responds to the student's query by uttering:

"Oh, well. Have you ever used a dictionary?"

Placing the punctuation mark *full stop* or *dot* after "Oh, well" is either a mistake or an error and is incorrect. Here, "Oh, well" is not an independent sentence and cannot be considered as one. It does not convey a full meaning; it is not semantically independent and does not have a subject and predicate, neither present nor omitted. It can be considered a conventional utterance, an interjection or exclamation or filler, but cannot be a separate sentence by itself.

"Oh well" as a full sentence and with full stop at the end, has a meaning irrelevant to the context of this conversation. If "Oh well" is used for that unrelated sense, it has no comma in the middle, between the words "Oh" and "well". In that case, the meaning would be expressing mild disappointment or implying a situation has to be accepted as is because nothing can be done about it. In this context, the relevant usage is "Oh, well ..." as a part of the sentence and not an independent one by itself (Grammarist.com, 2022; Cambridge English Dictionary, 2022; Collins English Dictionary, 2022). The usage relevant to this

context intends to convey a meaning like "I see, then..." and the relevant form to that meaning is "Oh, well," before the rest of the sentence. The correct form is:

"Oh, well, have you ever used a dictionary?"

The teacher replies by asking the student a question about his prior experience and knowledge. In order to respond to the student's query, the teacher briefly analyzes his current level of information using a question about his experience and if he has "ever used a dictionary".

Majid, the student, starts the third adjacency pair of the conversation by uttering:

"Actually, I haven't. But I've heard that using a good English dictionary can really help me learn English better."

This states that, Majid's decision to obtain a good dictionary is for the purpose of learning English better, and not, for example, translating texts.

Majid has decided to obtain a dictionary because he has *heard* a good dictionary can substantially help him with language learning. The word "*really*" indicates that Majid thinks the effect of using a good dictionary on language learning is of considerably high importance and believes using a good English dictionary drastically helps with learning English.

Majid has reached to this conclusion by what he has heard. It is not known from where he has heard about the importance of using a good English dictionary, but it is probably not from attending private English classes, as he has to rely and depend on his English teacher at school as the source of further information.

The person or persons who have told Majid using an English dictionary is helpful or Majid has heard the idea from might be his friends, though there is not a clear and certain clue in the text.

Mr. Iranmehr confirms Majid's idea in response in the sixth turn of the conversation (the second turn in the third adjacency pair) by saying "That's right."

He then continues by providing advice on the topic the student has asked him to. He utters:

"... . First, I recommend a learner's dictionary."

The discourse marker "first", indicates that this is the teacher's first and perhaps most fundamental advice on choosing a dictionary.

The student does not know what a *learner's dictionary* is. He begins a new adjacency pair and asks, "What is a learner's dictionary?"

It is reasonable to say that, the word "first" in Mr. Iranmehr's utterance suggests that he himself is going to give more advice and information without asking and even if the student did not ask, he probably would himself give the details.

The teacher, Mr. Iranmehr, answers his question by telling the student the target audience a learner's dictionary is designed for and the help it can offer for the intended target audience. He utters:

"It is designed for foreign students. It also helps them learn English better."

The first sentence is about the group of people the learner's dictionaries are designed for. The second sentence informs the use, benefit and practical purpose of this type of dictionaries according to the teacher.

It is arguably unclear why the word "also" has been used in the second sentence. The word also usually indicates that there are some other statements about something in addition to those mentioned earlier or some other ideas of equal importance or similar nature to those proposed before are going to be proposed, but using also in the second sentence the teacher utters in his fourth turn (the eighth turn of the conversation) does not appear to contain an idea of that kind. It is unknown whether the word "also" in this conversation refers to another purpose, benefit, use or function of learner's dictionaries or another characteristic of these dictionaries has been mentioned. A reader can observe that none of these possible semantic roles for the word also is present in the two sentences. One might ask whether the word also indicates that in addition to the fact that learner's dictionaries are designed for foreign students, they "also" help them learn English better. Such a usage is unnecessary and clumsy. The topic of the dialogue is about dictionaries helping in language learning and when it is said that these dictionaries are designed for foreign students, it is self-evident, obvious and apparent that they "help" them with language learning.

In the first turn of fifth adjacency pair, Majid asks, "Is there only one type of it?"

This question is unlikely to be asked by a person who does not know what a learner dictionary is. If a person does not know what something is, she or he is unlikely to ask about its possible types. Majid has just been told about a learner's dictionary and what a learner dictionary is. Asking such a question subtly implies he already knows something about the types of dictionary before the teacher tells him. One might argue that Majid asks the question to know and make sure he can find one of these dictionaries easily by simply using the term "a learner's dictionary" and no other specifications are necessary when shopping one. For that reason, a better alternative or replacement could be:

"Can I find one just by telling the shopkeeper I want a learner's dictionary?"

Or:

"How can I choose the best learner's dictionary?"

In the question "Is there only one type of it?" Majid wants to know whether learner's dictionaries come in only one type or more. Attributing this utterance to Majid is simply because of attributing the intended information (= answer to the question) to the teacher. This has contributed to making the conversation unnatural and inauthentic.

In response to Majid's question about types of learner's dictionaries, Mr. Iranmehr answers:

"No, in fact dictionaries have different types, levels and sizes"

It is worth mentioning that here there is no distinction between all dictionaries and the learner's dictionaries in terms of having different types, levels and sizes, but the student's question was about learner's dictionaries.

In this utterance of Mr. Iranmehr, he first gives a negative answer to the student's question on whether these dictionaries have only one type. He then tells the student that dictionaries come in different types, levels and sizes.

After the teacher tells the student about the diversity of dictionaries in types, levels and sizes, the student asks about each of these characteristics exactly in the same order. The student asks about each of these three specifications in a turn after he gets the answer to the previous question. The questions are about the recommended type, level and size, respectively.

In the next turn, Majid asks the teacher the type of dictionary he suggests.

"What type do you suggest?"

This question is asked in reaction to receiving the piece of information that dictionaries have different types, levels and sizes. After the student knows of the diversity in types, levels and sizes of dictionaries, he asks the type the teacher recommends for him. The question Majid asks is in the scope of pedagogy, educational methods and language learning concepts, as the teacher is expected to know about these areas to answer the question with regard to the specific needs of the student.

Mr. Iranmehr utters in response:

"I suppose a monolingual dictionary is more suitable for you, because you can find word information in English."

The word "suppose" reduces the firmness, certainty, intensesness and extremeness of the answer. It makes the answer less decisive.

The teacher advises the student to use a monolingual dictionary. This advice is in response to the student's question on the type of dictionary the teacher recommends. The teacher recommends using a monolingual dictionary (English-English) because in such a dictionary the word information is given in English.

Majid, asks about the level of the dictionary he should use in the next turn (the thirteenth turn of the conversation which is his seventh turn):

"And what about levels?"

As mentioned earlier above, each of the characteristics of a suitable dictionary he needs are enquired in a separate turn and sentence in the order mentioned by the teacher in the tenth turn of the conversation.

Mr. Iranmehr answers by introducing the frequently-used three categories of levels and then recommending one of them. He utters:

"Well, there are usually three levels: elementary, intermediate and advanced. For you as a high school student, an elementary one is OK."

Based on what the teacher says, he believes a high school student should use a dictionary of elementary level. Although almost all the conversation is in relatively formal language, the informal adjective OK has been used for the level which is suitable for the student.

In the fifteenth turn of the conversation, Majid asks:

"Do I need a small size one?"

The combination "small size one" is grammatically incorrect. The correct form is "small-sized one", however, in this sentence within this conversation, the word "size" is unnecessary. It has been mentioned earlier and anyone who knows the meaning of the word "small", would definitely know it is about size. It could simply be: "Do I need a small one?" or if using the word size in the sentence was insisted, it would be "And about (regarding) size..., do I need a small one?"

Asking this question indicates that Majid has some idea about the specifications of the dictionary he needs. Earlier in this conversation, he says he has never used a dictionary, but he can generate a suggestion like this (suggesting a small dictionary) himself.

Mr. Iranmehr replies:

"Yes, a pocket dictionary. You can carry it wherever you go."

This utterance contains information about both the recommended size and the reason why it has been suggested. It also contains an educational idea of self-teaching (autodidacticism): carrying an English dictionary wherever the learner goes. The teacher recommends this idea, as mentioning it here indicates approval of the idea.

Majid seems interested in the idea and approves of it. He then proposes a new issue about using dictionaries. He utters:

"Oh, it's very good. And hmm..., is it expensive?"

Now that he has found out the specifications of the dictionary which is suitable for him, he is concerned about the price of the dictionary he needs. The interjection "hmm..." might indicate all, some or one of the following meanings:

- Hesitation and reluctance about asking whether the dictionary is expensive
- Embarrassment or shyness—thinking it might be inelegant to ask about the price of something necessary for studying
 - Trying to remember the question which he has planned or intended to ask; knowing a question he has thought about has not been asked yet, but does not remember it at first.
- Trying to ask another question or trying to remember which necessary question has not been asked yet.

The teacher answers:

"No, such dictionaries are not expensive. By the way, you can use a free online dictionary, too. And also there are some free dictionaries for PCs and apps for smart phones."

The teacher reassures him that the dictionary he needs is inexpensive and is not high-priced. To comfort him even more, the teacher proposes alternative choices and ideas. The teacher puts forward the idea of using online dictionaries or the dictionary applications for computers and smart phones. Repeating the word "free" twice indicates that the alternative suggestions are put forth for eliminating the concern about the cost of the dictionary.

Majid says in response:

"Thanks, that's a good idea, but I'd like to use a pocket dictionary."

Although Majid is a teenager and most teenagers nowadays are interested in digital and electronic devices and solutions, he prefers using the *hard copy* of the dictionary. He would rather use a pocket dictionary instead of internet websites or applications which serve the same purpose. Majid approves of the idea of electronic dictionaries, but favors the dictionary in form of a book. Uttering the sentence "... that's a good idea" might be for the purpose of not being abrupt to suddenly refuse the suggestion of using electronic dictionaries.

Inclusion of this part of the conversation in which Majid tells the teacher his preference is using a pocket dictionary might be for the purpose of encouraging the students (textbook audience) to use books, instead of apps and websites. Perhaps the authors have intended to persuade the students to use paper dictionaries through attributing this desired behavior to the character of the conversation who is a student.

This conversation is the longest conversation of the textbook in terms of the number of the turns and adjacency pairs. It is the only conversation whose scenario occurs in an education setting (school classroom).

The aim of the conversation based on the table of contents in "Map of Vision 3" is "talking about dictionaries". In real life situations and communicative needs, it rarely happens that a person talks about dictionaries. Daily life's verbal and spoken communication rarely happens in such a situation or scenario. As the

main objective of the conversation is providing the students with information on the characteristics of a dictionary and choosing a dictionary, it would be better if the topic were proposed in a reading passage and a topic of higher communicative value and authenticity were chosen for the conversation instead of it.

In this conversation, a person's (the teacher's) workplace is the place the conversation occurs. This is one of the three conversations with reference to a workplace and occupational activity.

The relationship between the teacher and the student is of service provider-client which is similar to the relationship between the nurse and the patient in the first conversation of the textbook.

Like the first conversation of the textbook, in this conversation the expression "Excuse me" has been used for initiating a conversation, signaling a request and addressing the intended person. In the first conversation, the patient uses this sentence to get the attention of the nurse before asking a question and in this conversation the same thing happens when the student wants to begin the conversation with the teacher for the purpose of asking questions and getting information.

4.2.3.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

The conversation has been included in the textbook for the purpose of familiarizing the students with the specifications and characteristics of a suitable dictionary for them. Also, some patterns for requesting help and asking questions are presented within the text.

In the conversation, a student who has heard using a dictionary can help him with language learning asks his teacher to provide him the information he needs to choose the suitable dictionary.

4.2.3.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

A student named "Majid" is going to choose a dictionary that best serves his learning needs. He asks his English teacher for information, recommendation and advice on choosing the dictionary that is the most useful for him.

The student uses formal language and linguistic patterns of politeness in starting the conversation and asking the teacher for help.

The relationship between the student and the teacher is that of agent-client to a high extent. It is also the relationship between a person who refers to an expert and the expert he/she refers to. The conversation starts the same way as the first conversation of the book in which an agent-client relationship was evident. The same way in starting the conversation indicates semantic, pragmatic and socio-communicative similarity and relevance between the first conversation and this one.

4.2.3.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

According to the table of contents in the part titled "Map of Vision 3", the objective of this conversation is "talking about dictionaries". This means that the conversation is presented for the purpose of teaching the students what the characteristics and specifications of a dictionary are and which dictionary can be of help to them. Also, the idea of carrying a dictionary on the go is suggested as a tactic of language learning.

4.2.3.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

The conversation takes place at school and in the classroom. It is between a student and his teacher. Having heard a good dictionary is of great help in language learning, the student has decided to obtain one. He does not know what the characteristics of a good dictionary are and needs information about one. He asks his teacher for help and advice on choosing the right dictionary for him.

The situation and scenario is not authentic and does not have high communicative value as it entails a topic and situation with rare occurrence in real life. Information on a good dictionary could have been provided by means of a reading passage like the one already in the lesson.

4.2.3.1.3 Social Practice

Making polite requests is a major social and communicative theme in this conversation that is common between it and the first conversation of the textbook.

Politeness in asking for information is a quality of style the character who needs the information applies in his utterances.

It seems that there is a subtle discouragement against using electronic and digital learning tools and there is encouragement in favor of traditional ones. This possible trend and tendency is expressed in the students preference in using the traditional tool (= paper dictionary). If one wants to carry a dictionary, using her/his smart phone is more comfortable as nowadays a smart phone is carried everywhere for multiple purposes. Carrying a pocket dictionary along with the smart / feature phone which is a device most people carry these days, seems unnecessary trouble. It is not irrelevant if this part of the conversation's scenario is attributed to resistance against changes brought by the modern era.

4.2.3.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

The teacher's last name or family name, Iranmehr, is a reference to patriotism and nationalism. This compound name means "love [for] Iran", "Iran's love" or "Sun of Iran" in Persian and is therefore, a reference to patriotism and nationalism.

This conversation begins the same way as the first conversation: by using the sentence "Excuse me". This is an internal instance of intertextuality. It is also important that there is a notional and conceptual similarity between the two conversations (conversations one and three), because in both of them, a client (receiver of service) talks to an agent (provider of service). There is a side reference in conversation one towards education and knowledge, and the topic in conversation three is an educational topic.

4.2.3.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

Among the sociocultural values which are represented and referenced in the conversation and their representations are politeness when talking to a teacher, value and preciousness of education, patriotism, and traditionalism as favor of books to apps.

The teacher has authority in the interaction between the student and the teacher as he is the one with more information and knowledge and the student needs his knowledge.

4.2.3.2 Critical Observations and Notes

The conversation's situation is not an authentic communicative situation. Two Iranians, Majid and Mr. Iranmehr, are talking about dictionaries and they speak English. The topic and the situation of the conversation are rarely found in everyday conversations of real life. Information about dictionaries could simply be provided in a reading passage. There is already a reading passage in this lesson and all the information could be added to that text.

In daily life conversation and day-to-day speaking, people use language to communicate, interact and do things in many different situations. Examples of these situations are shopping, asking for directions, exchanging information, expressing feelings and emotions and reacting to them, greeting and chatting, etc. In this conversation, a person asks another person for information, but the topic is one rarely heard about in daily life conversations. How many times a year or in what percentage of yearly conversations, an ordinary person talks about dictionaries? This is especially worthy of debate and criticism because we see that the aim of the conversation section is "talking about dictionaries"!

4.2.4 Conversation Four

4.2.4.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.4.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

Conversation four is on page 61 and in "Listening and Speaking" section of lesson two. Like the other two conversations in this section in the other two lessons, the conversation does not have a description, but there is a textbox titled "Speaking Strategy" above it which declares the objective of the conversation. In this conversation, the aim is "talking about imaginary situations". It would be better if the conversation situation had a description, so that the students could have an idea about the conversation's situation before reading it.

There are two speakers of unknown identity in this conversation. The relationship between them is also unknown, although we can make guesses about its type. Their names are unknown and only their speaking turns are marked with green and red bullets.

The instructive objective of the conversation based on the table of contents and the textbox above the conversation, is "talking about imaginary situations" which is in fact the grammatical structure of unreal "if" clauses for present time (conditional type two). There is a line before the conversation and after the textbox which reads: "We use 'conditional type II' to talk about imaginary situations." This indicates that the instructional objective of this conversation is teaching this grammatical structure.

There are three adjacency pairs and six speaking turns in the conversation. Each speaker has an equal share of speaking turns. The topic of the situation and scenario of the conversation is choosing an activity for entertainment during the rain.

In the first turn, the conversation begins with the first speaker's utterance which is a description of the situation for opening the conversation:

"Oh look! It is raining so heavily."

The interjection "Oh" in the beginning of the first sentence and the exclamation mark at the end of it indicate surprise or excitement. The first speaker tells the other character of the conversation about what is happening now which is a weather event (precipitation or rain) which is intense and attention-getting. She or he (there is no clue or reference to the gender of speakers in this conversation) invites the other person to pay attention to the rain and directs her/his attention to it.

The first speaker uses the full form of "It is" and not the contracted form, yet we see the contracted form in the second turn of the conversation, as the second speaker utters:

"What would you do if it weren't raining?"

She/he asks the first speaker a question as a reaction to his/her utterance about the rainy weather. She/he asks what the first speaker would do if it weren't raining. The second speaker proposes a new topic in the conversation, which is

relevant, but relatively sudden and instant. The second speaker asks about the activity the first speaker has actually missed because of the rainy weather. She/he is asking about the first speaker's desired activity if the weather were different.

The first speaker answers:

"Hmm... if it were sunny, I would go to the park. I am really bored."

The first speaker needs a few seconds to prepare an answer. She/he needs a short time to think before he/she can answer the question. The interjection and exclamation "hmm..." is used as a filler at the beginning of the utterance as the speaker does not know what to say at first.

The first speaker says she/he is bored and if it were not raining, she/he would go to the park.

As the first speaker is bored and cannot go to the park, the second speaker comes up with a solution and gives a suggestion for an alternative:

"We can play one of our thinking games, instead."

This utterance shows the speakers share some thinking games ("*our thinking games*"), and therefore, there is a relationship between them which might be friendship or they might be family members or siblings. The second speaker suggests playing a board game. The phrase "thinking game" which has been used instead of board game implies the textbook authors who have written the conversation text have intended to value "thinking" and "exercise for the brain" (brain sport).

In response to the second speaker's suggestion, the first speaker utters:

"We could play 'Smart Kid' if Sina were home."

The first speaker says if a third person, named "Sina" were home, it would be possible for them to play a game named "Smart Kid".

This utterance indicates that the speakers of the conversation are at home, because if Sina *were home* they could play Smart Kid, as Sina could join them, too. This implies that the speakers of this conversation are members of a family and Sina who is not at home now, lives at *this* home, and is therefore another member of the family.

Based on the utterances of the conversation, "Smart Kid" is a game (as the second speaker says, "thinking game") which requires three players, because they could play it if Sina were home, too.

The final turn of the conversation also contains a suggestion. The second speaker who speaks the final turn utters:

"This one is also fun. Let's try it."

The phrase "this one" and the pronoun "it" both refer to another type of a game. The second speaker tells the speaker that although they cannot play Smart Kid because one other player is needed; there is another game which is also fun. He then suggests they try this game.

The characters in this conversation are nameless, but reference to the name "Sina" shows they are Iranian. Like conversations one and three, in this conversation two Iranian characters are speaking English to communicate in an interaction which is not relevant to common situations where English is used for communication. In other words, the speakers use English language in a situation where speaking English is basically unnecessary.

4.2.4.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

The conversation is between two family members, most probably siblings and is about doing an activity (playing a game) to entertain themselves when it is raining and they cannot go out.

4.2.4.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

The conversation is informal and casual. It is a conversation between two persons who live at the same home. It occurs when the weather is rainy and it is raining heavily. One of the speakers who starts the conversation by referring to the rainy weather, is bored and cannot go to the park despite her/his willingness due to the rainy weather. The second speaker suggests they can play one of the board games they have. The first speaker says if Sina were home, they could play a game named "Smart Kid". The second speaker suggests trying another game instead, saying this game is also fun.

Although the conversation is between family members, the only characteristic it has as an informal conversation is the use of contractions which occurs only once ("... if it weren't raining"). In the all other possible places, the full forms of the verb "be" have been used.

The conversation takes place at home between two members of a family. There is also reference to another family member who is currently outside home. The initial topic of the conversation is the rainy weather, but the second speaker asks a question about what the first speaker would do in an "imaginary situation" in which the weather is not rainy. She/he replies going to the park would be the activity she/he would do if the weather were sunny, because she/he is bored. The second speaker suggests playing a "thinking game" instead. The first speaker says if Sina, who is probably their brother, were at home, they could play a specific game. The second speaker replies by suggesting another game.

The second speaker is more practical as she/he is the one who suggests solutions and offers alternatives. The first speaker is the party who expresses the problems (not being able to go out, being bored, and impossibility of playing "Smart Kid" due to the absence of their sibling).

The discursive order in this conversation is a dialectic relationship between description and suggestion.

4.2.4.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

The main objective of the conversation is teaching the students how they can talk about imaginary (unreal) situations using the conditional type two or unreal if clause for present time.

There are three instances of using this structure in the conversation, both for third person singular ("it" and Sina).

Some marginal instructive by-products are description of rainy and sunny weather in sentence-making and generating suggestions.

4.2.4.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

The conversation occurs at home and between family members. It is about doing an activity which is done for fun while it is raining heavily and they cannot

go out. There are two imaginary situations described in the conversation text. The first one is about the rainy weather: "What would you do if it weren't raining?", "If it were sunny..." and the second one is about what they could do (= playing Smart Kid) if Sina were home.

The context of weather description is suitable for instructing unreal if clause (unreal conditionals type two). Weather is easily imagined and is not a subjective or mentally complex phenomenon and one can imagine its different states. A person's presence or absence is also a suitable base for illustrating the use of present time unreal if clause.

4.2.4.1.3 Social Practice

The first speaker's utterance in her/his second turn ("Hmm..., if it were sunny, I would go to the park.") and what the second speaker says in her/his second turn ("We can play one of our thinking games, instead.") imply that there is preference and favor for going out and outdoor activities, as they are going to play a "thinking game" *instead* of going out, because the latter activity is impossible now due to the rainy weather. The first speaker says if it were sunny (= if it were not rainy), she/he would go to the park and therefore, her/his first choice would be going out. It can be concluded that outdoor hobbies and activities are preferred and favored over indoor activities like board games. This can be what the authors think themselves consciously or unconsciously or it might be what they want to promote and advertise or something they find better for the student's life and therefore have included this in a part of the textbook to encourage outdoor activities. The reason to the claim about favoring outdoor activities is that the characters, especially the first speaker, are going to play thinking games when it is raining, otherwise, they would probably do something else, which is going to park in case of one of the speakers.

4.2.4.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

Three people are represented and referred to in the text of the conversation. Two of these three persons are the two speakers (the first and second speakers) and the third person is Sina who is not at home. He also lives at home and if he

were home, the trio could play "Smart Kid". This inclusion and arrangement might imply author's tendency for traditional more populous families and households which were mainly typical of the past time and are now less frequently found.

4.2.4.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

The first speaker begins the conversation by referring to the rainy weather, but the second speaker changes the topic of the conversation and redirects it. It is the second speaker who manipulates the conversation, proposes alternatives, suggests activities and invites to actions. She/he is more active and the first speaker is more passive. The second speaker in fact determines what the duo should do and is the active party in decision-making.

More populous homes and preferring outdoor activities are two cultural elements and value-related aspects of the conversation.

4.2.4.2 Critical Observations and Notes

It would be better if the conversation participants had names.

Despite the fact that the conversation which acts as a sample of English speaking, is between two Iranian persons (referring to a third person named Sina indicates this), its communicative value is at an acceptable level.

The authenticity of the conversation is limited, as the language style is not as informal as one expects a conversation like this to be. A conversation at home is usually expected to be informal, but there are instances of using full forms instead of contracted forms, eliminating the single sign of informality in the conversation text.

4.2.5 Conversation Five

4.2.5.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.5.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

The fifth conversation of Vision 3 textbook is on page 75 and is the first of the two conversations of the third and last lesson of the textbook. It is in

"Conversation" section of lesson 3 and is between a father and his son. There are six adjacency pairs and twelve turns in the conversation and both the conversation participants (conversation parties or speakers) have the same number of speaking turns in the conversation.

The description above the conversation reads:

"Emad and his father are traveling to Guilan. On the way, in Manjeel, Emad sees huge turbines."

This description briefly introduces the two conversation characters and tells the reader about the situation they are involved in. It also informs the reader about the critical event or the root occurrence which constructs the base of the conversation.

The aim and objective of this conversation according to the table of contents in "Map of Vision 3" is "talking about wind turbines"! So, the students are expected to be able to talk about wind turbines after reading and practicing this conversation!

Emad, the son, is surprised by seeing the "huge" wind turbines in Manjeel when en route to Guilan. He directs his father's attention to the wind turbines and begins the conversation. Seeing the wind turbines has stimulated his curiosity. In the first turn (the opening turn) he utters:

"Daddy, look at those big fans!"

He calls the wind turbines "big fans" and this indicates that he does not know what they are. What he says reveals he is surprised, amazed and astonished by what he sees, but has no idea what they are.

The word "*daddy*" is a more informal and childish form of the word "dad" which is informal itself. Using the word daddy implies informality and friendliness and suggests the son and his father have a close and casual relationship. For a boy at the age of Emad (based on the audio track of the conversation), it is a bit too informal and childish to call his father daddy instead of dad. The word daddy, has other meanings, especially as a slang or colloquial term, but the word dad is more limited to the concept of a father (a male parent).

In the second turn of the conversation, Emad's father responds to his son's surprise by telling him what the objects he sees are:

"They are actually wind turbines."

Emad has never heard the term "wind turbine" and is unfamiliar with it. He has no clue what a wind turbine is, as he utters in the third turn of the conversation:

"Wind turbines?"

Asking this question in this way (repeating what one has just heard) indicates total unfamiliarity. In the fourth turn of the conversation, Emad's father answers:

"Yes, wind turbines are used to produce electricity from wind power."

In this utterance, Emad's father is literally teaching him what wind turbines are used for. His sentence is an informative statement.

In the fifth turn of the conversation, Emad opens a new adjacency pair and expresses his unawareness and unfamiliarity about the concept of producing electricity from wind by uttering:

"I know electricity can be produced from water and sunlight. How might it be generated from wind?"

Both Emad and his father use formal words when it comes to scientific explanations, as if they were in a science class.

To answer the question of his son, the father utters:

"Well, a wind turbine works the opposite of a fan. Instead of using electricity to make wind, a turbine uses wind to make electricity. It is a type of clean energy."

This is the longest turn of all in this conversation, spoken by Emad's father. In this utterance, the father informs his son about how electricity is produced from wind. He briefly explains the process by proposing the opposite process as a logical example. He adds, "it is a type of clean energy" to mention the environmental benefit of producing electricity in this way.

Emad remembers something and expresses the contents of his mind about what he has remembered:

"These wind turbines remind me of what I read about using wind power in Yazd's buildings."

Emad has remembered the tradition and practice of constructing specific towers in traditional architecture of Iranian city of Yazd, These special structures

in buildings serve as natural air conditioning systems. They are also of historical and cultural value.

Mentioning Yazd's "wind towers" is related to recognition and acknowledgement of the historical and cultural heritage and achievements as well as celebrating and commemorating them. This is relevant to patriotism and nationalism.

This sentence also indicates that Emad is into reading. He also reads about his nation's heritage.

In the eighth turn of the conversation, the father replies:

"You mean wind towers?"

He clarifies what his son has just said by mentioning the exact term related to the concept or idea he has proposed in his utterance. Using the phrase "wind tower" here gives the impression and atmosphere of reading the English translation of two Iranian citizen's speech. This reduces the authenticity and originality of the conversation. The phrase "wind tower" which is the proposed equivalent of the Persian word "بادگیر" (/bʌdɡir/) brings about the impression that what we read in the text of this conversation is in fact the translation of a conversation between two Iranian persons and not a true English conversation.

This question is for clarification and informing purposes and is not an enquiring question, as the father knows exactly what the son means and wants to remind or teach him the exact term for the towers.

In the first turn of the fifth adjacency pair (the ninth turn of the conversation), Emad confirms his father's clarification and describes the use of the special towers as means of utilizing clean energy:

"Yes, they are natural air cooling systems and can be used instead of electrical air conditioners. This is another source of clean energy, isn't it?"

Emad explains and describes how beneficial and helpful these "wind towers" are as clean alternatives to electric air conditioning devices. He then uses a tag question to "elicit agreement" as proposed in the first lesson of this textbook.

Emad's father responds:

"Yes, it is. An excellent type of clean energy!"

In this utterance, Emad's father emphatically and enthusiastically confirms the local and native sample of clean energy utilization proposed by his son.

There is a shift of topic in the final adjacency pair of the conversation. In the sixth and last adjacency pair, the topic is changed to a new one, though it is relevant to the preceding utterances.

Emad proposes a new topic and requests a family trip to Yazd. He asks:

"Daddy, can we travel to Yazd this Norooz?"

Emad asks for a family trip to Yazd for the "Norooz" holidays. The reference to Norooz and mentioning travelling during the Iranian New Year holidays are references to elements of local and native (Iranian) culture.

Emad's father answers:

"That's OK with me. Let's check it with others."

This utterance indicates Emad's family is a democratic one. Decision-making is not the exclusive right of the father and he does not consider himself to be the only and decisive decision-maker, as others' opinions matter, too. So, it is not enough to obtain his approval and the issue should be checked by others as well.

4.2.5.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

This conversation is the third and last conversation which is placed in "Conversation" section. The table of contents in the part "Map of Vision 3" considers its topic and objective to be talking about wind turbines. The conversation has two speakers: an adolescent boy named Emad and his father. They are on their way to Guilan and when they are in or around the town of Manjeel, the son sees the wind turbines which provoke his curiosity.

4.2.5.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

The conversation is between a father and his son. It is started by the son and has the themes of questions-and-answers, fact confirmation, information exchange and reasoning on similarity and relevance of samples and examples of a concept or idea (mentioning two samples of "clean energy").

When the father and the son arrive in Manjeel or pass by the town, the son notices the large wind turbines and is surprised as they are new and unfamiliar to him. He reacts verbally by grabbing and redirecting his father's attention to the wind turbines, but picks a wrong self-made name for them as he does not know their names, function and simply what they are.

Once the real name of the objects is introduced to the son, he asks further questions about their function and usage. When the father mentions the concept of clean energy in explaining the function of wind turbines, it reminds the son of reading about a specific structure in traditional architecture and construction of the old buildings of Yazd. Wind turbines and Yazd's wind towers are two samples of using clean energy, having a purpose in common: to use a natural kind of energy (here, the wind) which does not produce pollutants.

The main element in the conversation which serves as the foundation and base, is the curiosity and exploratory attitude of the boy. This starts and leads the conversation and facilitates its main purpose.

Except for using the word daddy twice as the term of address for calling the father, an exclamation mark at the end of one utterance and shortened sentences with omitted components (like the two-word utterance "Wind turbines?" in the third turn, which is a sentence and question in terms of communicating a full meaning), the language in the conversation is formal; even using the contracted form "it's" instead of "it is" at the end of the sixth utterance has been avoided and the full form has been used.

4.2.5.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

The main purpose of the conversation, based on the textbook's table of contents, is teaching the students talking about wind turbines. This is an odd purpose for an EFL textbook conversation and lacks enough communicative authenticity and value. The conversation also includes three instances of using passive voice which can be considered as sample input for the grammar section of the lesson (in the grammar section of lesson three, another form of using passive voice is introduced which is using modals with verbs in passive voice) as well as a sample pattern for asking questions, answering them and providing explanations.

It is apparent in the conversation that an authentic instance or sequence of language use has not been provided in the conversation, as the topic, context, situation, characters and the theme are all local and there is no real reason for using a foreign language. As a translated text of a dialogue between two people cannot be considered a suitable instructional conversation, this conversation is not an adequate instructive conversation.

4.2.5.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

The situation and context in which the conversation's scenario occurs is formed when an adolescent boy observes large wind turbines in Manjeel on the way to Guilan when travelling with his father. The observation provokes his curiosity and urges him to ask questions. The son asking questions and the father answering them generate the framework and pivot for the conversation.

4.2.5.1.3 Social Practice

The conversation involves verbal and oral interaction between a father and a son along with references to historical and traditional architecture of an Iranian city, family life and environmentalism.

4.2.5.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

There is a sense of endorsement and appreciation towards using clean energy which is a reference to environmentalism and *green movement's discourse*. The conversation's text has approval positive attitude about utilization of clean energy and subtly encourages it in full compliance with the other sections of lesson three.

Mentioning an element or structure of Iranian architecture and referring to a traditional practice in local style of building construction in an Iranian city indicate authors' intention to acknowledge, recognize and promote Iranian achievements and historical accomplishments of Iranian culture. A reference to a historical and cultural fulfillment of a civilization as an example of reaching a

desirable goal (here, utilization of clean energy) implies tendency to nationalism and patriotism.

4.2.5.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

Encouraging the students to ask questions, promoting explorative pursuit and advocating curiosity are among the presented and implied themes in the conversation which have roots in questing knowledge as a value. The explorative spirit of Emad in this conversation represents the expected and desired behavior of asking questions.

Inclusion of reference to an achievement of Iranian civilization in Yazd is related to nationalism, patriotism and provoking nationalistic pride.

4.2.5.2 Critical Observations and Notes

This conversation does not represent using English language in an authentic and realistic context or situation. Communicative functions of English language, including utilizing the language as lingua franca, foreign language or second language do not exist in this conversation. Two characters (Emad and his father) who are Iranian nationals talk about two samples of clean energy, of which one is international and the other is local and domestic. One of the characters asks for traveling to Iranian city of Yazd for Nowrouz holidays and the other conversation participant agrees. This is another sign that shows they are Iranian persons. Such a situation is not a realistic instance of authentic English language usage and cannot be considered as the context of a real communicative conversation occurring in real life. It is more similar to a translation of a conversation between two people speaking a language other than English (here, Persian).

The topic is not of frequent use in real life. A very brief look at world renowned international textbooks which have been bestsellers of TEFL/TESOL/ELT industry and have been described as successful textbooks by teachers and learners would show that in such textbooks the topics of conversations are useful, beneficial and helpful for real life situations and events.

Talking about wind turbines rarely happens and is not of frequent use, nor does it require special conversation tactics and subskills.

4.2.6 Conversation Six

4.2.6.1 Application of Fairclough's Three-dimensional Model

4.2.6.1.1 Characteristics of the Text

The sixth conversation of Vision 3 textbook is the last conversation of this textbook and is on page 89 in "Listening and Speaking" section of lesson three. This conversation has three adjacency pairs and six turns. The names of the conversation characters have not been provided, but it is clear based on the text of the conversation (the second turn or the second turn of the first adjacency pair in which the second speaker utters the word dad: "*That was great, dad*") that it is between a father and his daughter or son. Each speaker's turn has been marked with either a green or a red bullet before their utterance.

Like the other two conversations in "Listening and Speaking" section, there is no description given before the conversation text, but the instructive objective of the conversation is mentioned in the textbox titled "Speaking Strategy" which is located above the direction before conversation text. The aim of the conversation based on the content of this textbox which is exactly the same as the proposed objective or topic in the table of contents in "Map of Vision 3" part, is "talking about an activity before another activity in the past".

The direction (guideline) before the conversation and after the Speaking Strategy reads:

"We use the 'past perfect tense' to talk about an event that happened before another event in the past."

This indicates that the goal of this conversation is teaching the grammatical structure of "past perfect tense" and its contextual usage.

The conversation is started by the father and is ended by the daughter/son. The father asks three questions in the conversation and what the son/daughter utters is for the purpose of answering the father's questions. The only participant that asks questions is the father. The son/daughter has the larger share of utterances.

The conversation begins by the father's utterance:

"OK, Tell me about the picnic. What did you do?"

The father wants to know about the things his daughter/son has done when on a picnic. He is interested in knowing about the activities his son/daughter has been engaged and involved in during the time he/she has been on a picnic recently.

The son/daughter replies:

"That was great, dad. We played volleyball and had a barbecue."

In this utterance, the youngster or adolescence mentions two activities she/he had done. One is playing a sport and the other is having a barbecue which is an outdoor food-preparing activity usually done when people go camping or go on picnics.

What the father says and asks in reaction is a bit odd:

"Oh, come on! Did you do anything fun?"

It is a rather unusual reaction and question. Why does the father think that playing volleyball or having a barbecue is not fun? It is uncommon and weird to say these activities cannot be considered as fun. It especially gets stranger as there is some sign of emphasis: "Oh, come on!"

The son/daughter answers:

"Yeah, it was all fun. Before we played volleyball, we had taken some
photographs."

In the first sentence, the son or daughter confirms and reaffirms that all they did was fun. To provide a more detailed and more complete answer, she/he mentions doing an activity before playing volleyball which she/he had not mentioned earlier in the conversation.

The activity not mentioned earlier in the conversation is taking some photos. It is weird the authors of this textbook insist on using the word "photograph", as they have used it before in the description before the first conversation in lesson one. The reason for the authors' insistence and emphasis on using this word is unknown. The word "photo" is usually used in everyday speaking and even writing and full form "photograph" is getting obsolete and is too formal. When native speakers simply use the word "photo" instead, there is no

reason for using the word "photograph" in a conversation between a father and a daughter/son.

Taking some photos seems to impress the father much more than playing volleyball and having a barbecue. The father says:

"Great! Did you do anything in the afternoon?"

The father probably asks about the afternoon because playing volleyball was mentioned before having a barbecue and having a barbecue is supposed to be preparing food for lunch which is the meal served at noon. As taking the photograph was done before playing volleyball, the time in the afternoon seems to remain empty. So the father asks if they have done anything in the afternoon.

It seems the authors have made and used this time sequence for actions (before, after) to present the use of past perfect grammatical structure.

In response to the father's question about the activities done in the afternoon, the daughter/son replies:

"Oh, something interesting! After we had eaten lunch, we flew our kites. That was fantastic because we had made the kites ourselves."

The son/daughter enthusiastically tells his/her father about flying "*their*" kites in the afternoon. When the father asks about the afternoon, the son/daughter happily remembers something and says: "Oh, something interesting! ..."

The son/daughter reports flying the kites was "fantastic" which indicates it has been enjoyable, pleasurable and so much fun. He/she attributes this being fantastic to the fact that they had made the kites themselves.

Throughout this conversation, the daughter/son uses the pronoun "we" six times, once in the second turn, twice in the fourth turn and three times in the last (sixth) turn of the conversation. This "we" most probably refers to the group of friends which gives the speaker an identity of being a member of a group doing recreational activities together.

4.2.6.1.2 Discursive Practice: Production and Consumption of the Text

The sample conversation is between a father and his offspring whose gender we do not know, as there is no reference to the gender of the second speaker (= the child). The father is eager to know about his child's experience on the picnic.

It seems this picnic has been either the first or one of the first occasion(s) the son/daughter has gone on picnic with his/her friends and without his/her father or a family member.

The son/daughter reports and narrates what his/her group has done.

The authors have used the order and sequence of doing picnic activities as an imaginary sample timeline to teach the correct usage of past perfect when used for describing past events of different order.

4.2.6.1.2.1 Communicative Event and the Discursive Order

The communicative event consists of a dialogue between a father and his son (or daughter) about what he/she and their group have done when on a picnic. The conversation occurs after the picnic and in which, different activities the group has done are reported based on their order and sequence and in response to the father's questions.

Like most parents, the father in this conversation is interested and eager to know about his son's (or daughter's) experience and things he/she does. Therefore, he asks questions about the activities he/she has been involved in on the picnic.

There are very few clues to the informal style of the language in the conversation. Using the word "dad", the interjection "oh" and using the idiomatic expression "Come on!" could be considered as some elements which indicate informal language. Using the word "photograph" is contradictory to use of informal language. The conversation is between a father and his child, so it is expected to be informal.

4.2.6.1.2.2 Instructive Level: Instructional Purpose

The instructional purpose of the conversation is teaching the past perfect tense. The usage and application of past perfect tense have been presented via the conversation.

The conversation presents the use of past perfect tense for describing past event(s) which happened before some other past occurrences.

4.2.6.1.2.3 Situational Level: Context and Scenario

In this conversation, the situation and context is a dialogue between a father and his daughter or son. The father asks questions and the son/daughter answers the questions. The questions answers are about a recent picnic the son or daughter has just come back from.

4.2.6.1.3 Social Practice

In this conversation, a boy or girl is talking to his/her father and is answering his questions about what he/she has done as member of a group, or in fact, what the group has done as whole. A family is the smallest unit of the society and in this conversation, a member of a family is talking about his/her experience in the group of his/her friends.

4.2.6.1.3.1 Intertextual and Referential Analysis: Ideological and Political References

Based on the utterances of the father, taking photos and flying the kites one has made herself/himself are of more enjoyment and value than playing volleyball and having a barbecue. This preference and choice indicates that this character in this conversation favors arts and crafts to athletic activities, sports and cuisine.

4.2.6.1.3.2 Sociocultural Aspects and System of Values: Dominance, Inequality and Bias

The father asks three questions in this conversation which makes it a bit like an interrogation. This is kind of relevant to the traditional relationship between children and their parents, in which parents have the right to question and interrogate their children and the authorities in family life and the children should report to the parents.

The authors have consciously or unconsciously implied that if one makes something himself or herself, then it feels fantastic for him or her to operate it. This is a reference to the value of independence.

4.2.6.2 Critical Observations and Notes

Using conversations for teaching grammar is a practice and approach most globally respected textbooks do not follow. Grammar sections in these textbooks are independent and conversations are mainly focused on and concerned with teaching patterns of speaking language as groups and chunks presented without grammatical analysis and focus. Using correct grammar in spoken language is also presented in conversations, but the conversations provide real life communicative input for the necessary communicative tasks required in contexts and situations of daily life, and correct grammar is also presented in authentic and realistic utterances.

Although this conversation is better than those in which two Iranian nationals are talking about Iranian matters, in terms of communicative value and authenticity, but it still does not prepare students for any real life speaking need or communicative task.

4.3 General and Holistic Analysis

Analyzes of some important aspects and elements of the six conversations of Vision 3 textbook have been discussed below.

4.3.1 Introduction and Overview

Effective instructional conversations within language teaching textbooks are expected and required to serve a variety of purposes and provide a number of solutions and opportunities. Conversations in textbooks are sources of linguistic input and sample patterns for acquiring the subskills, tactics and techniques of speaking skill. They present language use and illustrate language rules. Textbooks conversations depict the functional relationship of context, situation and language usage. Learners' use of textbooks conversations acts as a means of skill development for the learners. The contents of the sample conversations in textbooks convey linguistic, pedagogic, communicative and cultural messages of high importance. For some learners who do not access other tools and means, textbook conversations are the sole provider of linguistic input for development of speaking skill and communicative competence.

Instructive conversations which cannot serve these purposes and do not provide rich learning opportunities are in need of revision or omission.

Like any other linguistic sequence, utterance or text, textbooks instructional conversations also include and accompany ideological messages which affect the way they are used and treated in classrooms and by learners and teachers. Any text carries and conveys ideological content relevant to its purpose, the intention of its composer(s) or creator(s) and its processes of production and consumption. Textbooks conversations should be analyzed for ideological aspects and elements and revised if necessary, due to the fact that the ideological aspects and elements affect their efficacy in a number of ways including influence on pedagogy and necessary methods of instruction, risks of cultural mismatches or conflicts, compliance or contradiction with learner's existing ideology and culture etc.

4.3.2 Gender

Gender is an important part of a person's identity regardless of its definition, boundaries and cultural differences, characteristics, requirements or specifications. As people's identities influence their communication with others, factors such a gender also affect communication in different ways.

The clues to characters' gender are names, references in the text and audio track voices, when applicable.

It is noteworthy that in all the conversations in which the gender of the characters is known, the conversation participants or speakers (characters) are of the same gender; in other words, in all the conversations, either two males (conversations three and five) or two females (only conversation one) speak to each other and there is not a conversation in which people of opposite genders talk.

4.3.2.1. Number of male speakers and characters

There are 12 characters or speakers in the six conversations of Vision 3 textbook. Each of the six conversations has two participants.

Of the twelve characters, gender of seven characters is specified and known and there is no information about gender of the remaining five, as no clue, reference or evidence exists.

There are five male speakers in the conversations of Vision 3 textbook.

Male characters are the participants of conversations three and five and one of the characters of conversation six. The roles of the male characters are student, teacher, son and father (2 times).

4.3.2.2 Number of female speakers and characters

Out of the seven characters with known gender, two are female. The only conversation with female speakers is the first conversation in lesson one in which the nurse and Sara (the patient) are female characters.

4.3.3 Age and Relationship

People's age is part of their identity, self-image and others' view on them. In all types of communications, the relationships between the parties are important. In conversations, the relationships between people contribute to roles in conversations, linguistic and textual style, nature of interaction, word choice, etc. Age and relationship are among the characteristics that build part of the context and are also active in forming power relations.

It can be inferred with full certainty that of the 12 characters of conversations, four are minors (adolescents) and four are adults. The two speakers of conversation two ("Sam has not come to work...") are most probably adults and the two speakers of conversation four (Playing a game indoors in rainy weather) are most probably minors.

4.3.3.1 Number of instances of two peers speaking to each other

In conversations two (talking about a sick colleague or friend) and four (siblings or family members talking about choosing an activity in rainy weather), the speakers are of near or equal age.

4.3.3.2 Number of instances of conversation between a young speaker and a full-grown adult

In conversation one, an adolescent patient talks to an adult nurse.

In conversation three, a high school student speaks to his teacher.

In conversation five, a son talks to his father.

In conversation six, a daughter or son talks to his father.

In total, there are four occasions and conversations in which a minor (person below legal age or younger than 18) speaks to an adult. Two of the adults are fathers and one is a teacher. Another adult speaker is a nurse.

The target audience of the textbook is twelfth grade high school students who are adolescents (about 17.5 years of age). The authors have included four adolescent characters in the textbook conversations and therefore, have paid attention to the representation of the target audience.

4.3.3.3 Instances of conversation between a child and a parent

In conversations five (Emad travelling with his father) and six (son or daughter reporting on his/her picnic activities), the conversations are between a father and his child.

4.3.3.4 Instances of conversation between a student and a teacher

In conversation three, Majid, a high school student, asks his teacher for advice and guidance on dictionaries.

4.3.3.5 Conversations with Characters of Unknown Relationship or Age

Although guesses can be made, there is uncertainty in determining the relationship and age of speakers of conversations two and four.

4.3.4 Power and Dominance: Distribution of Authority

In conversation three, the teacher has authority due to his knowledge and expertise. The student's respect for him indicates his dominance. The teacher also has the larger share of utterances.

In conversation five, Emad asks his father for a trip to Yazd during Nowrouz holidays. Requiring the father's approval indicates his authority, though the authority is shared with other members of the family as well.

In conversations one, three and five, the adult who is more knowledgeable and more informed has the larger share of speaking and has certain type and level of dominance and authority within the domain of being the source of information or knowledge.

4.3.5 Place

Below is the list of the locations or places where the conversations occur.

It is worth mentioning that the only towns and cities which are mentioned in the conversations of the textbook are Tehran (hometown of Dr. Gharib, conversation one), Manjeel and Yazd (conversation five, the former is the town with wind turbines and the latter is the city with wind towers). Guilan is the only province with direct reference to its name.

4.3.5.1 List of places where the conversation scenario occurs

1. Hospital (Children's Medical Center): Conversation one
2. Workplace (Probably): Conversation two, but also conversations one, two and three
3. School and/or classroom: Conversation three
4. Home: Conversation four
5. In Manjeel, on the way to Guilan while travelling: Conversation five
6. Home (Probably): Conversation six

4.3.5.2 Indoors and Outdoors

Of the six conversations, three certainly occur indoors, two probably take place indoors and only one definitely occurs outdoors.

Conversations one (hospital), three (school) and four (at home in rainy weather) occur indoors. Conversations two ("Sam has not come to work...") and six (father talking to child on the picnic) probably happen indoors, though there is not decisive clue or evidence. Only conversation five (seeing Manjeel wind

turbines) happens outdoors. Outdoor activities are the topic of conversation six, but the conversation itself might not occur outdoors.

4.3.5.3 At School

In conversation three, Majid, a high school student, talks to his teacher during a break inside the school or classroom.

4.3.5.4 At Home and In the Family

Conversation four, in which one of the speakers cannot go to the park because of the rain and the two speakers choose to play "thinking games" is a conversation that almost definitely occurs at home.

Conversation five is between a son (Emad) and his father, but occurs outdoors while on a trip.

Conversation six, in which a daughter or son reports to her/his father on the picnic activities probably occurs at home while the father and the child are home.

4.3.5.5 At Work and within a Workplace

Conversation one transpires at a hospital, which is the workplace of one of the speakers (the nurse).

In conversation two, absence of a mutual acquaintance at work due to illness is discussed.

In conversation three, a high school student talks to his teacher at school. School is the teacher's workplace.

→

4.4 Numeric Differences

Table 1 Numeric Differences

Parameters ↓	Specifications and Characteristics ↓	Frequency (Number)	Conversations ↓	Notes ↓
Speakers' Gender →	Male	5	3, 5 & 6	Majid, Mr. Iranmehr, Emad, Emad's Father & an unknown speaker's father
	Female	2	1	Only the nurse and the patient (Sara)
	Unknown / Uncertain	5	2, 4 & 6	In conversation 2, there is also a reference to a non-speaker absent person named Sam, who is a male (name suggests). In conversation 4, there is also a reference to a non-speaker absent person named Sina, who is a male (name suggests).
Relationship between the Speakers →	Nurse – Patient	1	1	
	Friends or Colleagues	1	2	Based on context and content-based clues
	Teacher – Student	1	3	
	Siblings or Friends	1	4	Based on context and content-based clues
	Father – Son (Might be Father – Daughter in Conversation 6: Uncertain)	2	5 & 6	Conversation 6: Text evidence: Utterance of the second speaker (child)
Speakers' Age →	Adults	4	1, 3, 5 & 6	Conversation 6: Text evidence: Utterance of second speaker (child)
	Minors	4	1, 3, & 6	Conversation 6: Text evidence: Utterance of second speaker (child)
	Unknown / Uncertain	4	2 & 4	2: Probably adults; 4: probably minors (both uncertain)
Place of Conversation →	Hospital	1	1	
	Unknown, probably a workspace	1	2	Based on context and content-based clues
	School	1	3	
	Home	1	4	Based on context and content-based clues

	Outdoors	1	5	
	Unknown, probably home	1	6	Based on context and content-based clues
Reference to the Past →	Reference to past	3	1, 2 & 6	1: Life of deceased Dr. Gharib, establishment of the hospital 2: Sam's feeling unwell <u>yesterday</u> 6: Activities done on a picnic in the past
	No reference to past	3	3, 4 & 5	5: Yazd's wind towers mainly used in the past (present verbs)

Note. Numeric differences in characteristics of contexts and speakers of Vision 3's conversations.

4.5 Conversation Contents: Topics, Subjects and Values

The most important themes and/or topics of Vision 3 instructional conversations are education and knowledge, work, labor and occupation, preference for outdoor recreational activities or hobbies, the environmental issue of using clean energy and dialogue between a father and his son/daughter.

Home and family life is represented in three conversations, though in different ways. This indicates family life has been of value for the authors and the educational system.

References to education, knowledge and schooling can be found in two conversations. There is also a reference to "thinking games" and a reference to reading. This reveals that knowledge, education and being well-read have been among the important values in the underlying ideology and value system of the conversations and the textbook.

Two or three conversations occur in a workplace. This indicates that working has been an important issue and a topic of value in the ideological bases of the conversations and the textbook.

There is no non-Iranian speaker in any of the conversations. All the speaking characters are either certainly Iranian or there is no clue to their nationality or country of origin. Except for a reference to a non-speaker absent character named Sam in conversation two, no non-Iranian person has been referred to in any of the six conversations. In none of the conversations, English is

used as lingua franca or foreign language. Use of English language in the conversations seems absurd and baseless. There is not any situation or context in which two people of different nationalities or cultures talk to each other. This is in contrast to using English as a lingua franca and means of international communication and dialogue common around the world. No usual function of English language, such as talking to a tourist or a conversation during visiting a foreign country, can be observed in the conversations scenarios and contexts.

Formal language and lengthy sentences in the conversations make them more irrelevant to real life and more different from day-to-day speaking.

The topics of the conversations are of little relevance to real life frequent topics and issues which are most spoken about.

4.6 Discussion of the Results

Instructional conversations of Vision 3 textbook are inauthentic and are of low communicative value. There are only six conversations in Vision 3 textbook which is a too small number for a textbook with audience of high school seniors. The instructive conversations of Vision 3 textbook do not provide adequate and rich linguistic and communicative input for development of speaking skill. Linguistic and communicative input necessary for real life speaking tasks are not presented in the contents and contexts of the conversations.

In each of the three lessons of Vision 3 textbook, there are three parts containing reading passages and reading activity sections for reading comprehension improvement, but there are only two conversations in each lesson of which one is for teaching grammar and structures. In each lesson, two pages are dedicated to "Listening and Speaking", but three pages are allocated to reading skill.

Of the two pages assigned to Listening and Speaking parts, only one page is for speaking and even in that page, there is no activity in which role-playing, imitation or oral practice is done (After the conversation, "More Examples" are provided to reinforce structure leaning). Neither the conversations in "Conversation" parts nor those in the first page of "Listening and Speaking" parts have been required to be used for role-playing in any activity.

The parts "Grammar", "Writing" and even the conversations in "Listening and Speaking" parts all contribute in teaching grammar, but even conversations are not fully allotted for teaching speaking skill.

It can be safely and fairly declared that in Vision 3, less attention has been paid to speaking skill and the ability to make conversations. The main focus of Vision 3 textbook is on reading and grammar.

The authors have deliberately avoided the native and original culture of English-speaking countries. There are two or three instances of reference to indicators of patriotism and nationalism.

Concerning the ideological aspects and foundations of the conversations, the topics and contents of the conversations indicate that the ideological system of the authors and the official education system emphasizes on family life, education and knowledge, working, occupation and labor, as well as the politeness and traditional roles of people.

By reading the texts of conversations four, five and six, and comparing the frequency of their major theme and location of occurrence to the themes and places of other conversations, I got the impression that outdoor life and activities are prioritized over indoor activities.

In all the conversations in which two speakers with known gender talk to each other, the conversation is always between two people of the same gender. This may be related and attributed to authors' unconscious interpretation of Islamic regulations or the official education system's view on religious regulations.

Nationalism and patriotism are among the frequent themes and references in Vision 3 conversations.

The critical events of conversations one and five indicate and imply that the authors have intended to encourage asking questions and following exploratory pursuits among the students. In both of these conversations, seeing something provokes the curiosity of adolescent characters and as a result, they ask questions.

The ideological and sociocultural system of beliefs that has created the foundation and base for composing the conversations of Vision 3 is Islamic-Iranian ideology of the official education system.

Analysis of the contents, topics, themes and contexts of Vision 3 conversations showed that, these conversations adhere to the values of culture and ideology of the national education system and the authors. Also, the represented culture and ideology in Vision 3 textbook is Iranian and Islamic culture and ideology. Culture of English-speaking societies and countries has no place in any aspect of the conversations of Vision 3 textbook and has been left untouched and ignored.

Situations, contexts and scenarios of the conversations of Vision 3 textbook only represent a very limited proportion of real life issues, contexts and situations, and are therefore, unnatural and relatively irrelevant to real life matters. This makes it difficult for the learners to relate themselves to the conversations and their contents. The conversations occur in unrealistic situations and contexts and their topics are neither appealing nor related to normal daily life.

Vision 3 conversations depict English language use poorly and artificially. English language is used in the imaginary situations of these conversations in an inconceivable and unrealistic manner. In Vision 3 conversations, English is unrealistically used for communication of Iranian people in their local situations where using English is unnecessary, absurd and unreasonable. This approach reduces the benefit and usefulness of the instructional conversations for learners and makes them uninterested.

Conversations of Vision 3 textbook are inauthentic and represent unnatural fictitious and fabricated language which is the language of on people in nowhere!

Among the ideological and cultural aspects and elements of Vision 3 are traditionalism, male dominance and domination, value and preciousness of knowledge and education, politeness, honoring, acclaiming, commemorating and acknowledging the national culture, history and achievements and admiring honorable figures, and patriotism and nationalism as well as engaging in outdoor activities or intellectual activities.

Provision of rich and useful linguistic input for development of speaking skill by Vision 3 conversations is questionable. The conversations of Vision 3 textbook function poorly in terms of offering the necessary patterns and samples

for successful involvement in communicative tasks of the real life as a result of their inauthenticity and deviation from natural language and realistic life contexts.

Most teachers and learners agree that conversations of a textbook are expected and required to present and provide dynamic opportunities, fundamental guidelines and foundational patterns for development of speaking skill and gaining the ability to effectively communicate in situations people encounter in real life. This is a criterion Vision 3 conversations do not meet.

The quality of textbook conversations can be judged based on their similarity to corpuses of native speakers' speech, their inclusion of real life speaking tactics and provision of contextual and communicative patters. In all these areas, Vision 3 conversations fail to serve the needs of learners.

Chapter Five
Summary, Conclusion, Implications and
Suggestions for Further Studies

5.1 Summary and Conclusion

Applying Fairclough's three-dimensional model to conduct critical discourse analysis of the instructional conversations of Vision 3 textbook for the purpose of exploring the ideological and sociocultural aspects of these conversations revealed that the conversations are inauthentic, unnatural and unrealistic and fail to provide adequate input and useful sample patterns for real life speaking.

Of the six conversations of Vision 3 textbook, three are in Conversation section and the other three are in Listening and Speaking section. The conversations are not realistic. Irrelevancy to real life situations and communicative needs and difference to native speakers' speech and linguistic production can be observed in the conversations of both sections.

The topics of the conversations are of low relevancy to day-to-day life and bear little usability in real life. High school seniors may hardly be attracted to the topics and the scenarios are not appealing to the target audience.

Absence of the culture of any English-speaking society and emphasis on national mainstream Persian-speaking culture cause the conversations to lack cultural integrity and harmony. Another major factor contributing to this lack of integrity which leads to inauthenticity and artificiality is exclusion and absence of situations or contexts in which English language is needed and is expected to play a role. Imagining two Iranians speaking English for an issue of a typical day bears little sense and is unnatural or even ridiculous.

The sociocultural and ideological elements, aspects and factors which are significantly tangible and prominent in the conversations are admiration and acclamation of national culture, history and honorable figures, patriotism, nationalism, predomination of male gender, politeness, respect for teachers and parents, high value of knowledge and education, exploratory approach to what one sees and prominence of family life or relations.

5.2 Pedagogical Implications

Results of this study can be used for revision of the conversations of Vision 3 textbook. Also, teachers can benefit from the results to create and design supplementary content and activities to compensate for the weaknesses of the conversations.

Familiarizing the students with some of the concepts and techniques of critical discourse analysis (CDA) is helpful and beneficial for enhancing their understanding of the contents of materials.

Reagan (2006) points out that, critical study of language has a high potential and functional usability for enhancement of people's social awareness and educating responsible educators and citizens.

According to Rahimi and Sharififar (2015), teaching methods of critical discourse analysis can improve critical thinking ability and motivation of students.

Abbasian and Malaee (2015) highlight the positive effect of teaching the principles of critical discourse analysis and its methods on reading skill and motivation for learning English in university students.

Teachers can improve the students' understanding of meanings and ideas of texts by familiarizing the learners with critical discourse analysis.

5.3 Suggestions for Further Studies

As parts of Vision 3 textbook other than conversations have been beyond the scope of this study, it is suggested that similar studies with critical discourse analysis perspective and approach explore different aspects of other parts and sections of the textbook.

It is suggested that the conversations and other parts of Vision 3 textbook and other Iranian secondary education English textbooks be analyzed using other models of critical discourse analysis.

Due to the fact that Norman Fairclough considers expression of messages and meaning with sign systems like pictures as a type of discourse and text (Yarmohammadi, 2014a,b&c) and his three-dimensional model of critical discourse analysis can be used for critically analyzing messages and meanings expressed by non-linguistic sign systems, it is suggested that the photos, pictures

and illustrations of the textbooks of Iranian middle schools and high schools be subject to critical discourse analysis.

Conducting comparative studies with critical discourse analysis approach, perspective and methodology for investigation of differences between foreign and Iranian textbooks is also suggested.

Appendices

Figures 7 – 15

Conversations of Vision 3 textbook in the order and sequence of the book and the analysis

 Sara has been in the Children’s Medical Center for a week. She has caught a terrible flu. The doctor told her to stay there to get better. There is a photograph of an old man on the wall. While the nurse is taking her temperature, they start talking.

Sara:	Excuse me, who is that man in the picture?
Nurse:	Oh, don’t you know him? Have you ever heard of Dr. Mohammad Gharib?
Sara:	I guess I have only seen his name in my English book, but I’m not sure about it.
Nurse:	Dr. Gharib was a famous physician.
Sara:	Oh,... can you tell me a little about his life?
Nurse:	Dr. Gharib was born in Tehran in 1288. After receiving his diploma, he went abroad to study medicine. In 1316 he became a physician and then came back to his homeland. In 1347 this center was founded by Dr. Gharib and one of his close friends.
Sara:	Really? I didn’t know that.
Nurse:	Dr. Gharib was also a generous man. He spared no pains

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to cure sick children. He was very friendly and helpful to poor families. Not surprisingly, he was regarded as a dedicated physician.

Sara: It's a pity! I didn't know such a great man.

Nurse: He was known as a distinguished university professor, too. The first Persian textbook on children's diseases was written by him. He taught medicine to thousands of students.

Sara: Oh, what a great man he was!

Nurse: By the way, it might be interesting to know that your physician was one of Dr. Gharib's students!

Sara: Really?! That's interesting!

Questions

Answer the following questions **orally**.

1. When was Dr. Gharib born?
2. Why was Dr. Gharib regarded as a kind physician?
3. Have you seen Dr. Gharib TV series?

Listening and Speaking

Speaking Strategy

Eliciting Agreement and Signaling Uncertainty

A. We use 'tag questions' for two reasons: eliciting agreement (confirming facts) and signaling uncertainty.

- Sam has not come to work. I've heard he's sick, isn't he?
- Oh, yes. He was not well yesterday.
- What's wrong with him?
- The doctors are checking his health condition.
- It isn't something serious, is it?
- I hope not.

More examples:

- He's really generous, isn't he?
- They are going to leave here, aren't they?
- This cannot be true, can it?

 Majid is going to choose a suitable dictionary for his English class. He is talking to his English teacher during the break.

Majid: Excuse me Mr. Iranmehr, I wonder if you could help me.

Mr. Iranmehr: Sure. How can I help you?

Majid: I'd like some information about a good English dictionary.

Mr. Iranmehr: Oh, well. Have you ever used a dictionary?

Majid: Actually, I haven't. But I've heard that using a good dictionary can really help me learn English better.

Mr. Iranmehr: That's right. First, I recommend a learner's dictionary.

Majid: What is a learner's dictionary?

Mr. Iranmehr: It is designed for foreign students. It also helps them learn English better.

Majid: Is there only one type of it?

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- Mr. Iranmehr:** No, in fact dictionaries have different types, levels, and sizes.
- Majid:** What type do you suggest?
- Mr. Iranmehr:** I suppose a monolingual dictionary is more suitable for you, because you can find word information in English.
- Majid:** And what about levels?
- Mr. Iranmehr:** Well, there are usually three levels: elementary, intermediate and advanced. For you as a high school student, an elementary one is OK.
- Majid:** Do I need a small size one?
- Mr. Iranmehr:** Yes, a pocket dictionary. You can carry it wherever you go.
- Majid:** Oh, it's very good. And hmm..., is it expensive?
- Mr. Iranmehr:** No, such dictionaries are not expensive. By the way, you can use a free online dictionary, too. And also there are some free dictionaries for PCs and apps for smart phones.
- Majid:** Thanks, that's a good idea, but I'd like to use a pocket dictionary!

Questions

Answer the following questions **orally**.

1. What type of dictionary does Mr. Iranmehr recommend?
2. What factors do you consider when you want to choose a dictionary?
3. What type of dictionary do you often use?

Listening and Speaking

Speaking Strategy

Talking about Imaginary Situations

A. We use 'conditional type II' to talk about imaginary situations.

- Oh look! It is raining so heavily.
- What would you do if it weren't raining?
- Hmm... if it were sunny, I would go to the park. I am really bored.
- We can play one of our thinking games, instead.
- We could play 'Smart Kid' if Sina were home.
- This one is also fun. Let's try it.

You may use the following to talk about imaginations, hopes, and wishes.

- What would you do if you were me?
- What would you do if you had wings?
- What would you do if you were a university student?

Conversation

Emad and his father are traveling to Guilan. On the way, in Manjeel, Emad sees huge wind turbines.

- Emad:** Daddy, look at those big fans!
- Father:** They are actually wind turbines.
- Emad:** Wind turbines?
- Father:** Yes, wind turbines are used to produce electricity from wind power.
- Emad:** I know electricity can be produced from water and sunlight. How might it be generated from wind?
- Father:** Well, a wind turbine works the opposite of a fan. Instead of using electricity to make wind, a turbine uses wind to make electricity. It is a type of clean energy.
- Emad:** These wind turbines remind me of what I read about using wind power in Yazd's buildings.
- Father:** You mean wind towers?

- Emad:** Yes, they are natural air cooling systems and can be used instead of electrical air conditioners. This is another source of clean energy, isn't it?
- Father:** Yes, it is. An excellent type of clean energy!
- Emad:** Daddy, can we travel to Yazd this Norooz?
- Father:** That's OK with me. Let's check it with others.

Questions

Answer the following questions **orally**.

1. Where are Emad and his father?
2. Has Emad ever traveled to Yazd?
3. What types of clean energy can you find in your city or village?

Listening and Speaking

Speaking Strategy

Talking about an Activity before another Activity in the Past.

A. We use the 'past perfect tense' to talk about an event that happened before another event in the past.

- OK, Tell me about the picnic. What did you do?
- That was great, dad. We played volleyball and had a barbecue.
- Oh, come on! Did you do anything fun?
- Yeah, it was all fun. Before we played volleyball, we had taken some photographs.
- Great! Did you do anything in the afternoon?
- Oh, something interesting! After we had eaten lunch, we flew our kites. That was fantastic because we had made the kites ourselves!

You may use the following structures to talk about two activities in the past.

- Before I, I had
- After I had, I

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چکیده

هدف این پایان‌نامه انجام تحلیل گفتمان انتقادی بر روی مکالمه‌های کتاب درسی ویزن ۳ بر اساس مدل سه‌بعدی فرکلاف بود. تحلیل محتوا، موضوعات، طرح کلی، شخصیت‌ها، موقعیت‌ها، بافت کلام و ویژگی‌های متنی مکالمات نشان داد، ابعاد ایدئولوژیک (جهان‌بینی)، فرهنگی و عناصر متنی، معنایی و محتوایی مکالمات شامل بسامد و تکرار بیشتر شخصیت‌های مذکر، ارزش‌دهی به دانش و آموزش، افتخار به تاریخ و فرهنگ ملی و مشاهیر، ملی‌گرایی و میهن‌دوستی و تشویق به کنجکاوی هستند. تحلیل همچنین نشان داد، مکالمات غیراصیل، غیرواقع‌گرایانه و غیرطبیعی بودند. کاربردها و فواید استفاده از تحلیل گفتمان انتقادی در تدریس زبان انگلیسی شامل کاربرد در بازنگری و اصلاح مواد و متون آموزشی، ایجاد مواد آموزشی و فعالیت‌های تکمیلی و بهبود تفکر انتقادی در میان یادگیرندگان هستند.

کلیدواژه‌ها: تحلیل گفتمان انتقادی، کتاب‌های درسی، مدل سه‌بعدی فرکلاف، مکالمه‌های آموزشی، ویزن ۳

سازمان اسناد و کتابخانه ملی جمهوری اسلامی ایران

با استناد از شورای عالی اسناد و کتابخانه ملی جمهوری اسلامی ایران و با استناد از کمیته ملی اسناد و کتابخانه ملی جمهوری اسلامی ایران:

تمام کتب و اسناد و سایر منابع اطلاعاتی که در اختیار این سازمان قرار گرفته است، در صورت لزوم و در صورت نیاز، به سایر دستگاه‌ها و سازمان‌ها و افراد حقیقی و حقوقی، در صورت درخواست و با رعایت ضوابط و مقررات، می‌تواند در اختیار آن‌ها قرار گیرد. این امر به شرط آنکه در اختیار آن‌ها قرار گیرد، به منظور استفاده علمی و پژوهشی و در راستای اهداف این سازمان است. همچنین، این سازمان موظف است، در صورت لزوم، اقدامات لازم را برای حفاظت و نگهداری از اسناد و کتب خود، در اختیار آن‌ها قرار دهد. این امر به شرط آنکه در اختیار آن‌ها قرار گیرد، به منظور استفاده علمی و پژوهشی و در راستای اهداف این سازمان است. همچنین، این سازمان موظف است، در صورت لزوم، اقدامات لازم را برای حفاظت و نگهداری از اسناد و کتب خود، در اختیار آن‌ها قرار دهد.

مهم‌ترین وظایف این سازمان عبارتند از: گردآوری، نگهداری، حفاظت، دسترسی و انتشار اسناد و کتب ملی و اسناد و کتب خاص. همچنین، این سازمان موظف است، در صورت لزوم، اقدامات لازم را برای حفاظت و نگهداری از اسناد و کتب خود، در اختیار آن‌ها قرار دهد.

استاد ارشد، دکتر سید سعادت آملی
تاریخ: ۱۳۸۷/۰۷/۲۴
محل امضاء:

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

« صورت جلسه دفاع از پایان نامه کارشناسی ارشد »

با تأییدات خداوند متعال و با استعانت از حضرت ولی عصر (عجل الله تعالی فرجه الشریف)

جلسه دفاعیه پایان نامه کارشناسی ارشد آقای / خانم محمدمهدی معادی خواه شماره دانشجویی

۳۹۷۱۱۱۷۱۱۲۲ رشته زبان و ادبیات انگلیسی گرایش زبان و ادبیات انگلیسی

تحت عنوان: تحلیل گفتمان انتقادی مکالمات کتاب درسی ایرانی ویژن ۳ بر اساس مدل فرکلایف با کاربردهای آموزشی برای تدریس زبان انگلیسی

با حضور هیأت داوران در محل سالن دفاعیه دانشکده ادبیات و زبان ها در تاریخ ۱۴۰۰/۱۱/۰۷ تشکیل گردید

در این جلسه، پایان نامه، مورد قبول ● مردود ○ تمدید مهلت دفاع (طبق صورت جلسه) ○ و با درجه:
عالی ○ بسیار خوب ● خوب ○ قابل قبول ○ غیر قابل قبول ○ مورد دفاع قرار گرفت.

نام و نام خانوادگی	سمت	مرتبۀ علمی	امضاء
دکتر حمیدرضا دولت آبادی	استاد راهنمای اول	استادیار	
دکتر حمید ورمزبازی	داور خارجی پایان نامه	استادیار	
دکتر علی محمد محمدی	داور داخلی پایان نامه	استادیار	
دکتر زهرا رجیبی	نماینده تحصیلات تکمیلی	استادیار	

جهت ارایش فضا در جدول، هر یک از ست ها که در پایان نامه مسابق ندارد، حذف گردد.

دفاع مطابق مجوز اخذ شده و ضوابط و آیین نامه دوره کارشناسی ارشد صورت پذیرفته است و نتیجه آن مورد تأیید تحصیلات تکمیلی دانشکده است.

و من الله التوفیق

دانشگاه اراک

دانشکده ادبیات و زبانهای خارجی
گروه زبان و ادبیات انگلیسی - آموزش زبان انگلیسی
پایان نامه دریافت درجه ی کارشناسی ارشد

عنوان:

**تحلیل گفتمان انتقادی مکالمات کتاب درسی ایرانی و اثرن
۳ بر اساس مدل فرکلاف با کاربردهای آموزشی برای
تدریس زبان انگلیسی**

نگارش:

محمد مهدی معادی خواه

استاد راهنما:

دکتر حمیدرضا دولت آبادی

زمستان ۱۴۰۰